

D 2.1 Analysis and Diagnosis Report

Regional context analysis for conditions for circular economy and industrial symbiosis.

Mission / Sub-mission methodology.

Region of Dalarna (Lead)

30/04/2025

Project information	
Project title	European Circular Economy Innovation Valley: the European "dance floor" for circular regions
Acronym	ECIV
Project URL	http://www.eciv.eu/
Grant Agreement n.	101161155
Call	HORIZON-EIE-2023-CONNECT-03
Call Topic	HORIZON-EIE-2023-CONNECT-03-01: Implementing co-funded action plans for connected regional innovation valleys
Type of Action	HORIZON Programme Cofund Actions
Project start/end date	01.09.2024 / 31.08.2029
Project duration	60 months
Project coordinator	Delia Sola Jiménez (GN)

Project No. 101161155. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Deliverable information	
Deliverable n.	D2.1
Work package n.	WP2
Deliverable title	Analysis and Diagnosis report
Lead beneficiary	DAL in collaboration with NMS (regions of Dalarna, Värmland and Gävleborg)
Participants	GN, SODENA, SNN, GRO, FRY, DTH, UGRO, IPF, NMS, NOR, MIGB, SPW, IAL, HURC, SE, IbioIC, ACR+
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Due date	30.04.2025
Document status	Final V
Document version number	V2
Document type*	R
Dissemination level	Public
*Legend = R – Report // DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // DEC – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // DMP – Data management plan // OTHER – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Government of Navarra	GN	C	ES	PB
2	Society for the Development of Navarra	SODENA	B	ES	SME
3	Northern Netherlands Alliance	SNN	B	NL	PB
4	Province of Groningen	GRO	B	NL	PB
5	Province of Friesland (Fryslan)	FRY	B	NL	PB
6	Province of Drenthe	DTH	B	NL	PB
7	University of Groningen	UGRO	B	NL	UNI
8	Friesland Innovation Foundation	IPF	B	NL	NGO
9	Region of Dalarna	DAL	B	SE	PB
10	Region of Värmland	VÄR	B	SE	PB
11	Region of Gävleborg	GÄV	B	SE	PB
12	Region of Normandy	NOR	B	FR	PB
13	Ministry of Innovation and Growth	MIGB	B	BG	PB
14	Public Service of Wallonia	SPW	B	BE	PB
15	Innovation Agency Lithuania	IAL	B	LT	PB
16	Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council	HURC	B	FI	PB
17	Scottish Enterprise	SE	B	UK	PB
18	Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre – University of Strathclyde	IBioIC	B	UK	UNI
19	Association of Cities and Regions for Sustainable Resource Management	ACR+	B	BE	OTH

*Legend = Role in the Project: C – Coordinator // B – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development // UNI – Higher or secondary education establishment // SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // NGO – Non-Governmental Org // PB – Public Body // OTH – Other

WORK PACKAGES AND LEADERS

Work Packages Name		WP Leader
WP 2	Design of Transformative Innovation Programme and Regional Action Plans for circular for interconnected Regional Innovation Valleys	DAL / NMS (DAL, VÄR, GAV)

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How to quote this document

Author(s)/Organization. (Year). Title of the deliverable/report (Report No. or Project No., if applicable). *Publisher or Institution*. URL (if online)

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPSI	Observatory of Public Sector Innovation (OECD)
TIP	Transformative Innovation Programme, ECIV's interregional innovation strategy
RAP	Regional Action Plan(s)
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-governmental organization
RIV	Regional Innovation Valleys
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package
MOI	Missions oriented Innovation
MIPO	Mission-oriented Innovation Policy Observatory, Copernicus Institute, Utrecht University
MOIS	Mission-Oriented Innovation and Industrial Strategy (UK)
IIPP	UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose
CE	Circular economy

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2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Circular Economy Innovation Valley (ECIV) project is a collaborative initiative uniting 19 partners across thirteen European regions and nine countries, carefully selected for their innovation capacity, dedication to the circular economy, and potential for synergistic collaboration.

ECIV's mission is to drive the creation of a more sustainable and prosperous Europe by transforming traditional EU value chains into interconnected, innovative, and circular systems, ultimately establishing a thriving circular economy ecosystem by 2050.

This transformation is crucial for achieving the EU's climate neutrality goals, supporting industrial transition, strengthening industrial autonomy, and enabling a broader green transformation by significantly reducing waste and decreasing the extraction of raw materials.

The project employs a novel "dance floor" approach to connect stakeholders and facilitate the development of circular solutions to shared challenges within regional industrial value chains.

Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on developing a transformative innovation program and regional action plans for the interconnected innovation valley. This involves employing a mission-oriented innovation strategy, defining specific sub-missions to address key circular economy challenges. The combined top-down and bottom-up design approach ensures the strategy's validity and sustainability by harmonizing efforts and engaging regional actors.

The project anticipates managing significant changes within the stakeholder ecosystem, including the emergence of new value chains and the phasing out of others, while adapting to diverse policies and cultures.

The project will leverage these diversities to foster innovation.

Key objectives of Work Package 2 include:

- Analysis of existing regional networks, assess ICT maturity, and map circular economy policies to inform innovation programs and regional action plans.
- Analysis of value chain gaps and business opportunities stemming from sustainability requirements to understand the demand for circular solutions.
- Redefinition and evaluation of regional circularity strategies, supporting new value chains
- Formulation of actionable sub-missions (top-down) and prototype strategic project portfolios (bottom-up) representing initial, strategically aligned collections of project concepts that address regional needs and contribute to the overall mission of the ECIV project. This will be done collaboratively with regional stakeholders.

This report presents the initial analysis (M1-M7) of the circular economy conditions within

the participating regions. It provides a comprehensive understanding of regional contexts, challenges, and opportunities, encompassing policy aspects, strategic planning, and stakeholder involvement.

The analysis identifies key challenges and opportunities to inform the development of transformative innovation programs and regional action plans (RAPs). This work will continue until M12, culminating in the delivery of the ECIV's interregional innovation strategy, a Transformative Innovation Program (TIP) based on a mission-oriented innovation approach.

Further analysis during months 8 -12 will include gap analysis for new circular value chains within the RAP framework, continuous and in-depth stakeholder mapping, and the exploration of business opportunities informed by ECIV's sub-mission design and the 'Dance floor methodology' (WP3).

Key Findings – conditions for circular economy:

Our analysis reveals a complex interplay of challenges and opportunities in the transition to a circular economy across participating regions, which are widely aligned with EU-wide trends.

Challenges:

- **Skills Gap:** A critical shortage of skilled labour hinders the implementation of circular economy initiatives.
- **Regulatory Barriers:** Inconsistent and fragmented regulations across regions create obstacles for businesses adopting circular models.
- **Business Model Transformation:** Existing linear business models dominate, making the shift to circular models challenging.

Opportunities:

- **Strong Regional Collaboration:** The ECIV project facilitates unprecedented collaboration between regions, creating synergies and leveraging combined resources to overcome challenges.
- **Growing Demand for Sustainable Solutions:** Increasing consumer demand for sustainable products and services creates a strong market incentive for the development and adoption of circular economy solutions.
- **Technological Advancements:** Innovation in areas such as material science, digital technologies, and waste management offer significant opportunities for developing efficient and cost-effective circular economy solutions.

Regional Context:

- **Varied Levels of Circularity:** Significant differences exist in current circularity levels across regions (Circular Material Use Rate, CMUR¹), ranging from 1.3% to 24.5% according to the EEA, indicating a spectrum from frontrunner regions to those with predominantly linear economies. This highlights the need for targeted strategies to address regional specificities.
- **Shared Aspirations and Approaches:** Despite these differences, all regions share a common goal of increased circularity, with existing strategies, guidelines, and financial instruments in place to promote CE. Key focus sectors include construction, food & agriculture, and manufacturing.
- **Smart Specialisation (S3/S4) strategies:** A key asset of the ECIV project is the presence of complementary Smart Specialisation (S3) strategies across the participating regions. This strategic alignment provides a significant advantage in developing an effective interregional innovation strategy, enabling the project to focus on areas of shared strength and build a competitive edge in the circular economy.

The combination of regional diversity and shared challenges, alongside EU-level policy momentum and varying implementation progress, creates both significant opportunities and persistent obstacles in the pursuit of a truly circular economy across the participating regions.

The ECIV project is strategically positioned to address these specific regional needs, leverage existing strategies, and contribute to broader EU-wide circular economy objectives.

The initial analysis phase has established a foundation for ECIV's mission-oriented innovation strategy. The key findings inform the design of targeted sub-missions, providing a clear and unified direction for the project's collaborative efforts. This process will harness the strengths and expertise of each region while proactively addressing common challenges. The resulting sub-missions will guide the development of transformative innovation programs and impactful regional action plans, accelerating the transition to a circular economy and maximizing ECIV's positive influence on the European landscape.

¹ The CMUR measures an economy's circularity. This is defined by the circular use of materials, which is approximated by the amount of waste recycled in domestic recovery plants minus imported waste destined for recovery plus exported waste destined for recovery abroad, divided by the material use. The material use is the sum of domestic material consumption and the aforementioned circular use of materials.

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/circular-material-use-rate-in-europe?activeAccordion=546a7c35-9188-4d23-94ee-005d97c26f2b>

3. Detailed analysis concerning conditions for circular economy and industrial symbiosis based on common methodology

The initial analysis of circular economy conditions and opportunities for industrial symbiosis across the ECIV regions served a crucial purpose: to prepare for the top-down design of the project's missions in month seven, March 2025.

This early phase of the innovation project presented a number of challenges, including establishing effective work routines among diverse partners with varying levels of circular economy development and navigating differences in data quality and existing analyses.

Given the project's timeframe a fully comprehensive, region-specific study including the procurement and creation of harmonised data sets for resource flows, industry turnovers and data-based network analysis for all partners was infeasible.

Therefore, the initial analysis leveraged existing data and analyses, supplemented by soft knowledge from regional representatives and stakeholder input.

To investigate circular economy conditions in the ECIV territories, a self-assessment was conducted using a combination of methods: two surveys, a SWOT analysis, and regional stakeholder workshops. This report **“Conditions for Circular Economy in ECIV Regions – Self Assessment” (Appendix 1)** presents the results of that assessment, focusing on identifying **synergies and patterns across regions** and highlighting observations that prepare for further discussion and analysis.

In addition to the self-assessment, the project team engaged in regular digital work meetings, workshops, and coaching sessions to introduce the mission-oriented process. These sessions, designed to prepare for the regional stakeholder workshops and mission design, explored methodologies such as speculative futures and scenario planning to foster innovative thinking.

More in-depth analyses will be conducted throughout the project on the basis of the interregional Submissions and in support of new circular value chains. The top-down submission design will be iteratively refined through a bottom-up approach involving extensive collaboration with our stakeholders, ensuring a robust and adaptable strategy.

Surveys and SWOT

The survey questionnaire and SWOT analysis were designed to comprehensively assess key aspects of the circular economy landscape in each region.

This included an examination of:

- Policies and incentives
- Strategies, targets and action plans

- Stakeholder mapping and circular practices
- Resource flows
- Funding and financing opportunities
- Local challenges and opportunities.

Feedback on the initial questionnaire led to refinements that broadened the scope to include multi-level policy instruments, industries beyond those specifically mentioned in regional strategies, companies involved in waste valorization, and a detailed mapping of incoming and outgoing resource flows in relation to the ECIV Sub-missions. For each priority sector, the survey also sought to identify specific expertise, key stakeholders, existing technologies for interregional collaboration, major scaling-up needs and challenges, and the role of social enterprises.

Due to inconsistencies in data quality and a lack of harmonized frameworks, empirical evaluation of the survey was limited. Therefore, strategic design decisions for the ECIV sub-missions were also informed by collaboration, reasoning, and negotiation during the top-down design.

The completed questionnaires served as a starting point for regional workshops, providing a basis for verifying challenges and opportunities, complementing the information gathered, and proposing potential synergies and common challenges with other regions. Following the finalization of questionnaires from all regions, a thorough analysis was conducted to identify these synergies and common challenges, informing subsequent project activities.

Key Common Challenges for Circular Economy Transition

The participating regions face several common challenges in their transition to a circular economy. These include:

- **Skills Gap:** A lack of skilled labour hinders the implementation and scaling of circular economy initiatives.
- **Regulatory Gaps:** The absence of harmonized regulations creates barriers to market access and interregional collaboration.
- **Budget Constraints:** Limited financial resources restrict investments in circular economy infrastructure and innovation.
- **Infrastructure Deficiencies:** Insufficient infrastructure, including digital infrastructure, hampers the efficient collection, processing, and distribution of circular resources.
- **Logistical Complexity:** The increased complexity of circular value chains, coupled with inadequate material flow control and traceability, poses significant logistical challenges.
- **Dominance of Linear Business Models:** Existing linear business models outweigh circular alternatives, hindering the adoption of circular practices.

- **Lack of Awareness:** Insufficient awareness and understanding of the potential benefits of the circular economy limit its adoption by businesses and consumers.

Key Common Opportunities for Circular Economy Transition

The participating regions share several promising opportunities to accelerate their transition to a circular economy:

- **Growing Awareness:** Increasing awareness among companies, policymakers, and academia regarding the benefits of the circular economy is creating a favorable environment for change.
- **EU Green Deal Initiatives:** The EU Green Deal and related initiatives, along with new R&D opportunities and synergies with decarbonization activities, present substantial opportunities for funding and collaboration.
- **Collaboration Potential:** Existing platforms, networks, and businesses offer a strong foundation for fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing.
- **Access to Resources:** Access to existing resources and recycling infrastructure provides a valuable starting point for developing circular value chains.
- **Increased Competitiveness:** New markets, industry transformation, and pilot platforms offer opportunities to increase competitiveness through circular economy practices.
- **Expertise and Skills Development:** Opportunities exist to increase expertise and skills in circular economy-related fields through training and education programs.
- **Policy Innovation:** There is potential for policy innovation to harmonize regulations and create a more supportive regulatory environment.
- **Funding Opportunities:** Various funding opportunities are available to support circular economy projects and initiatives.
- **Experimentation and Innovation:** A culture of experimentation and innovation can drive the development of new circular solutions.
- **Dynamic Industrial Sector:** The industrial sector is increasingly open to circular economy practices and is actively collaborating with universities on research and development.
- **Public-Private Initiatives:** Public-private initiatives and regional commitments towards the circular economy provide significant opportunities for collaboration and investment.
- **Public procurement:** as a means of strategically applying resources to circular economy initiatives

Regional Stakeholder Workshops

Eight of the nine participating ECIV regions conducted stakeholder workshops to validate and expand upon the initial circular economy analysis. The intent of these workshops was

to engage regional stakeholders in reflecting on identified challenges and opportunities and discussing local capabilities for moving forward.

The desired outcome was to generate ideas for potential sub-missions that were supported by regional stakeholders, providing the ECIV consortium with valuable insights into regional capabilities to inform the subsequent top-down sub-mission formulation process (March workshops).

WP2 Lead provided a general framework for workshop structure and prepared the workshop agenda, structure, and evaluation materials, acting as support to local facilitators.

Each region adapted the format and methodologies to best suit their specific conditions and contexts, employing diverse approaches. Local regional facilitators led the workshops, sending invitations and arranging the sessions, while regional stakeholders actively participated, sharing their thoughts and knowledge. All methodologies and results were documented for subsequent analysis (see Appendix 1).

The key results from these workshops are summarized below, organized by the two main reflection areas.

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional Analysis

- **Recognition of Challenges and Opportunities:** Stakeholders generally recognized the identified challenges and opportunities.
- **Common Challenges:** These included a lack of awareness and knowledge, financial constraints, regulatory and policy barriers, collaboration and networking issues, and technological/infrastructure challenges as well as the need for new business models.
- **Common Opportunities:** Public procurement, innovation ecosystems and collaboration, development of circular business models, policy and regulatory support, and education/workforce development were highlighted.
- **Reactions to the Analysis:** Reactions varied. Some found the analysis too broad and lacking in detail, while others were interested in the shared challenges across regions.
- **Missing Aspects:** Stakeholders felt the analysis needed more specificity, including sectoral data, regional economic structures, connections between impact and dependencies, and more detailed policy/regulatory information at different levels. The geopolitical context was also missing.
- **Surprising Aspects:** Some regions questioned the national circularity rates presented in the analysis.
- **Most Interesting Aspects:** Developing practical tools (e.g., circular business models), collaborative efforts, sector-specific strengths, and supportive policy frameworks were of particular interest.

Reflection 2: Capabilities

- Capabilities Needed Moving Forward:
 - Collaboration and Networking: Between industry, municipalities, and research institutions; cross-sector working groups; stakeholder involvement; and facilitating interconnection between companies.
 - Financial Resources and Support: For SMEs, developing new circular business models, coaching, impact assessment, funding innovation, and funding instruments for high-risk investments.
 - Skills and Knowledge Development: Circularity assessment, design skills, regulatory knowledge, and marketing; developing a toolbox for companies; increasing skills and workforce, especially in repair; and education/workforce development for circular economy skills.
 - Regulatory and Policy Incentives: Regulations to encourage circular practices and solutions, and public procurement.
 - Technical and Infrastructural Support: Improved waste collection and sorting systems, and scaling-up infrastructure.
 - Market Development: For recycled materials, and optimizing value chains within the EU context.
 - Consumer Awareness and Behavioural Change.
- **Available Capabilities:** Most regions have partially available capabilities and need to develop and strengthen them. A few regions have high availability due to engaged stakeholders. One region reported low capabilities and a need for external expertise.
- **Stakeholder Ownership:** A 50/50 split among the regions regarding high and partial ownership among stakeholders. However, the tendency to focus on localized problems creates challenges for stakeholders in embracing a broader interregional perspective and planning effective European collaborations to solve shared issues.

4. Diagnoses of the Gaps and opportunities based on existing GAP analysis and analysis of country profiles for circular economy on national (regional) and EU level including strategic European Value Chains.

To contextualize the regional analysis, a comprehensive review of existing Circularity Gap Reports at regional and European levels was conducted, including gap analyses of strategic European value chains. The key findings are summarized in the report **“GAP analysis and analysis of circular economy country profiles – ECIV” (Appendix 2)**, which

identifies existing gap analyses at regional/national and European/EU levels and highlights key insights.

Point of Departure

A **GAP analysis** is a strategic tool used to compare a current state with a potential or desired state. It helps identify the differences (or “gaps”) between the two states, allowing to develop strategies to bridge them. There are no GAP reports on circular economy for all nine regions. We have therefore also included other reports, Circular Economy Country Profiles, with similar content.

Methods and Sources

Two main sources have been used for the compilation of GAP analyses on the regional (& National) level: **Circularity Gap Reports (CGR)** and **Circular Economy Profiles (EEA)**.

On a European (& EU) level, **reports and statistics from EEA** have mainly been used. For value chains on a European (& Global) level, sources include reports from the European Commission, the EU project RegioGreenTex and the One Planet network.

CGR: Circularity Gap Reports

- provides a comprehensive GAP analysis, describing gaps between current and desired circularity with actions and policy recommendations
- published by the organization Circle Economy, which has been working since 2011 to promote a circular economy through research and collaboration

EEA: Circular Economy Country Profile

- not GAP reports, but provide an overview of current state and the way forward, including national policies, best practices and data and statistics compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Topic Centre on Circular Economy and Resource Use (ETC/CE).

	North Middle Sweden	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Wallonia	Gabrovo	Normandy	Navarra	Scotland	Lithuania	Northern Netherlands	European level
Full GAP-reports CGR	X						X		X	(global)
Country profiles EEA	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X*

Figure 1. Table over existing and accessible reports (Source: Appendix 2)

Key Insights

Current states regarding CE differ among the regions: Some regions are labelled more as frontrunners, whereas others are still more linear. Circularity rates range between 1.3% to 24.5% among participating regions/nations, according to EEA.

ALL regions have strategies working towards increased circularity: The ‘overarching’ desired state is the same among the regions. All have strategies and guidelines in place for CE, and some have laws steering in this direction. Financial instruments are also used in all regions to promote CE, etc.

Similar sectors are in focus in the majority of regions: This mainly includes the Construction sector, the Food and Agriculture sector, and the Manufacturing sector. Other ‘rather’ common sectors include Energy, Transport and Mobility, and Water.

Similar challenges and needs among the regions: This mainly includes behavioural shifts, harmonization of regulation, strategic planning, development of infrastructure, R&D, economic incentives, and jobs and skills/labour market.

Current state in the EU: The average circularity rate in the EU is 11.8% according to EEA. Europe consumes a higher proportion of recycled materials than other world regions, but improvement has been slow in recent years. Meanwhile, material demand is projected to increase over the coming years.

Strategies working towards increased circularity in the EU: Centred around a life-cycle approach, i.e: reducing raw material demand, activating eco-design requirements, promoting product service system models, extending product lifetimes, and shifting the waste sector to provide high-quality recycled materials for the industry.

Political momentum in the EU: The circular economy concept has gained political momentum in Europe. A comprehensive set of new circularity policies has been introduced at EU level, and national actions have intensified. Many nations are, however, at the early stages of implementation.

Existing and ongoing Research and Development in ECIV Regions

To support network creation and stakeholder involvement, a compilation of existing and ongoing research in the nine ECIV regions was conducted. The results were documented in a report titled **“Research and Development in the ECIV Regions” (Appendix 3)**, which focuses on identifying prevalent research areas and topics within the regions.

5. Methodology for the top-down formulation of ECIV Sub-missions

Early dialogue with the Missions oriented Policy Innovation Observatory at the Copernicus Institute, Utrecht (MIPO), the OECD Observatory of Public Sector Innovation (OPSI) and Vinnova, Swedens Innovation Agency focused on adapting mission-oriented innovation (MOI) principles to **the unique context of the ECIV project**.

The dialogue with MIPO showed that the TransMission framework, typically used for aligning regions within a single country, was deemed unsuitable due to the diverse scales and circular economy maturity levels of the ECIV partner territories.

Instead, the ECIV project will leverage the common European goal of transitioning to a circular society, focusing on stimulating innovation through open call funding for circular projects across the territories.

This approach emphasizes:

- Defining sub-missions that address real-world challenges (e.g., securing critical raw materials)
- Considering the interconnectedness of regional ecosystems from a mission perspective.
- Fostering collaboration across sectors to address bottlenecks and build circular value chains.
- Viewing initial projects as building blocks and prototypes towards larger-scale solutions and system demonstrators.
- Allow for development on different speeds, create a variable geography, harness energy from all partners.
- All (partners) need to be represented.
- Use criteria for missions to ensure they are actionable.
- Create a "Theory of Change" - from Mission into practice

Key considerations for designing effective ECIV missions include:

- Missions should be broad enough to attract attention and stimulate innovation.
- Missions should address interregional challenges and opportunities that are relevant across multiple regions.
- Missions should align with circular economy principles and contribute to resource efficiency.
- Missions should encourage collaboration across different sectors.
- Missions should address the most pressing challenges identified by the regions.

Best Practices

Inspiring examples of mission-oriented approaches

Mission-oriented approaches are transforming how governments and institutions address complex societal challenges, from climate change to technological transformation. By setting clear, ambitious goals and mobilizing resources across sectors, these strategies drive systemic change and innovation.

In this section, we highlight three examples that have informed and inspired ECIV's method

for designing Missions: The European Union's five missions, the UK Industrial Strategy, and Impact Innovation – Sweden's transition to a sustainable society.

The European Union's five missions

The European Union has incorporated five key missions into its €100 billion Horizon Europe research and innovation program (2021-2027). These missions focus on climate change adaptation, cancer, healthy oceans, climate-neutral cities, and soil health, see below². Designed to tackle complex societal challenges, they aim to deliver tangible solutions by 2030 through cross-sector collaboration, policy alignment, and public engagement.

The 5 EU Missions are:

- Adaptation to Climate Change: support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030
- Cancer: working with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure and solutions to live longer and better
- Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030
- 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030
- A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030

The Missions were developed through an **extensive consultation process involving experts, policymakers, industry leaders, and citizens**. The European Commission established Mission Boards, each composed of specialists from various fields, to define concrete objectives. These boards engaged in dialogue with stakeholders and citizens across Europe to ensure alignment with societal needs. The final Missions were officially announced in 2021, with a strong emphasis on achieving measurable impacts by the end of the decade.

Each mission receives dedicated funding within Horizon Europe, complemented by national and regional initiatives. Success relies on close collaboration among governments, businesses, researchers, and citizens, with continuous monitoring to ensure accountability and adaptability to emerging challenges. Each mission functions as a portfolio of coordinated actions—including research projects, policy measures, and legislative initiatives—designed to achieve a measurable goal that individual efforts alone could not accomplish.

The UK Industrial Strategy

In the UK, the concept of mission-oriented innovation has been central to **the government's Industrial Strategy**, particularly in addressing grand societal challenges and **driving long-**

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en

term economic growth. The Industrial Strategy was launched in 2017 and included several key missions aimed at improving productivity, driving innovation, and tackling major societal issues. These missions are designed to guide public and private sector collaboration toward achieving specific, measurable outcomes by 2030.

When the UK Industrial Strategy was first introduced it initially focused on four missions: Clean Growth, AI and Data Economy, Future of Mobility and Ageing Society.

The missions were identified in the Government's Industrial Strategy white paper through the lens of the mission-oriented innovation framework, identifying relevant cross-sectoral actors, bottom-up projects, and paths to delivery. However, since its initial implementation, the UK government has expanded the scope of the mission-oriented framework, including the addition of a fifth mission, Zero-Carbon Energy.

As part of UK government's Industrial Strategy, the Mission-Oriented Innovation and Industrial Strategy (MOIIS) framework was developed by the UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose (IIPP) to guide the implementation of mission-oriented approaches to innovation and industrial transformation.

While the Industrial Strategy sets out specific missions, the MOIIS provided the theoretical foundation and a more detailed methodology for implementing mission-oriented approaches to innovation and industrial transformation. MOIIS emphasized the role of the state in driving and coordinating innovation across sectors, ensuring that public and private efforts work together to achieve ambitious societal goals. The framework encourages long-term systemic change through collaborative innovation, policy alignment, and public engagement, shaping the UK's approach to its mission-driven strategy.

For each mission, the MOIIS Commission supported the government in refining mission frameworks to establish a bold and clear roadmap. By emphasizing cross-sectoral projects, the Commission aimed to stimulate innovation in ways that directly contribute to achieving each mission's goals.

The roadmaps developed under the MOIIS framework are not restrictive recommendations but rather illustrative guides that define the scope, methodology, and ambition of each mission. They highlight the need for diverse solutions and a broad range of policy drivers to drive progress. Figure 1 illustrates an example of a roadmap for the Future of Mobility mission.

Figure 2. The 'Future of Mobility' grand challenge (MOIIS Commission, 2019). Källa: Mazzucato, M., & Dibb, G. (2019). Missions: A beginner's guide. *UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose, Policy Brief series (IIPP PB 09)*

Impact Innovation – Sweden's transition to a sustainable society

Impact Innovation is an initiative that focuses on tackling some of the most significant challenges of our time. With a clear mission of creating a transformed, sustainable, and competitive Sweden, the initiative tackles complex societal issues through collaboration, innovation, and ground-breaking solutions. The goal is to develop innovative solutions that address real-world needs and drive the transition towards a sustainable future.

Impact innovations launched as a joint effort by the Swedish Energy Agency, Formas, and Vinnova, Impact Innovation is anchored in Agenda 2030 and the EU's social and environmental goals. The initiative aims to accelerate Sweden's transition to a sustainable society, strengthen its global competitiveness, and reinforce its position as a leader in innovation.

At the heart of Impact innovation is a mission-oriented approach to tackling some of the most pressing challenges in society. The initiative gathers actors from diverse sectors—

businesses, industry organizations, academia, research institutes, municipalities, regions, and civil society—to collaborate in ways that exceed short-term business interests. This approach emphasizes bold, long-term commitments to drive transformational change and systemic impact. Impact Innovation’s efforts are structured around five key programs that address different aspects of sustainability and societal transformation. Each program focuses on a particular challenge, working towards innovative solutions that can create broad, systemic change: NetZero Industry, SustainGov, Metals & Minerals, Shift Sweden and Water Wise Societies³

An example of this approach is seen in Water Wise Societies. Water Wise Societies works to ensure that water is available in the right quantity and quality, and that it creates good conditions for people, the environment, ecosystems and industries – despite a changing climate. Their mission is Sustainable water for all by 2050. However, to make the mission more **tangible and actionable it has been refined into three specific sub-goals or sub missions.**

The sub mission and its descriptions⁴ aim to set the direction for the program while engaging and mobilizing stakeholders for collaboration and joint action in the transition:

1. Wise Water Use
2. Resilient Water Supply and Management in Society
3. Healthy Lakes, Waterways & Groundwater

Figure 3. Water Wise Societies mission, sub-missions and tasks

³ <https://impactinnovation.se/en/programmes-overview/>

⁴ <https://waterwisesocieties.se/delmal/>

Each sub-goal is further detailed through specific descriptions and tasks. In total, 10 key tasks outline the current state, the desired future, and the necessary (system) changes to drive the transition. These tasks mobilize stakeholders, fostering collaboration and collective action. By addressing them, Water Wise Societies advances its sub-goals and contributes to achieving its overarching mission.

ECIV and the mission-oriented approach

After analyzing and understanding the different mission-oriented approaches employed the ECIV project has recognized the Water Wise Societies methodology as a valuable model for **driving systemic change**. Inspired by this, ECIV aims to adopt a similar mission-driven strategy to advance the transformation of the circular economy. This approach focuses on setting clear, specific sub-missions that provide strategic direction, ensuring that efforts are both actionable and measurable. By aligning stakeholders around a common mission, ECIV aims to mobilize diverse sectors to interregional collaboration and take collective action. These sub-missions will serve as guiding frameworks, fostering the engagement of stakeholders and enabling long-term, impactful change within the circular economy.

ECIV Mission-Method

The ECIV project has adopted a mission-oriented approach in its work to develop an Interregional innovation valley to drive transformation of towards a circular economy ecosystem in Europe. The mission-oriented approach is fundamentally about setting a clear direction for a broad mobilization of perspectives and resources towards a common goal. The ambition is to understand and change how today's system of factors and actors works and how it affects the prevalence of a challenge. The system perspective means that we look at wholes instead of individual parts.

It is an inherently iterative approach, grounded in a systemic understanding of the issue, which clearly defines problem, goal frames, and embraces experimentation.

Mission-driven innovation consists of four interconnected activities:

1. **Mobilize** across sectors to create shared understanding of the challenge – Engaging a broad range of expertise to define the problem from multiple perspectives.
2. Setting a transformation goal to **direct** efforts– Aligning efforts toward a shared objective that enables cross-sector collaboration and diverse solutions.
3. **Coordinating** and executing actions in a portfolio– Leading, managing, and implementing initiatives to achieve the mission.
4. **Learning** and scaling – Continuously adapting based on insights and expanding successful approaches.

Figure 4. The four fundamental parts of the missions-oriented approach. (Source: <https://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/isi/dokumente/> adapted by Ramboll and ECIV)

Creating an understanding of the current system

As part of defining a direction for the efforts in the ECIV project, the project started by analyzing the current state and ambitions in each region through looking at current policies and strategies for circular economy as well as identifying main challenges and opportunities in their current systems.

In the analysis a model describing five perspectives of a socio-technical system (figure 2) was suggested to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the system.

Figure 5. Five perspectives in a socio-technical system. (Source: Ramboll)

The depth of the analysis varies between the regions based on their different starting points. However, the analysis has created an understanding of each region's current state and highlighted opportunities between regions. The shared understanding of each region's current state has also fostered understanding and empathy between regions regarding their individual starting points.

The material from each region and their individual system analysis were then compiled into an interregional analysis showing shared focus areas, challenges and potential opportunities among the ECIV regions.

Stakeholder engagement to identify potential tensions and facilitate future co-ownership

To ensure the understanding of the system and its' challenges and opportunities are in line with the understanding of stakeholders and actor and to create an understanding for needs and drivers among stakeholders each region conducted workshops or focus group interviews with stakeholders. This validated the regional analysis as well as the interregional analysis and gave regional representatives an understanding of priorities among their local

stakeholders.

The results of this regional stakeholder engagement were presented for the other regions, building a shared understanding of current state of the combined system around circular economy with the ECIV regions. The results also contributed to the further development and detailing of the interregional analysis.

Through the initial desktop analysis and stakeholder involvement, the regions have developed an understanding of the overall system as well as their local systems. This understanding has been built through mobilization activities, such as examining signals in strategies to identify areas with the potential to create a sense of co-ownership. The stakeholder involvement has enabled identification of potential tensions between different interests and created conditions for formulating missions that feel relevant and engaging.

Figure 6. Model describing the ECIV top-down Sub-missions design process. (Source: adaptation of an innovation funnel based on “The Impact Entrepreneur: Building a New Platform for Economic Security in Work” Rowan Conway, Charles Leadbeater & Jennie Winhall, The RSA, 2019)

Designing Missions

“Mission-oriented innovation has the potential for transformative systemic change. Yet it cannot deliver without fundamentally innovating the ways in which we innovate. ”

“There is always a design phase; the issue is whether it is done consciously or not. An unconscious design phase is likely to be full of assumptions, missed opportunities and

limited engagement. It will tend to reinforce business-as-usual rather than transformation, and negative outcomes rather than positive co-benefits. We must instead define and engage an active and participative design process for missions.”

(Source: Designing Missions- Mission-oriented innovation in Sweden— A practice guide by Vinnova, 2022)

It is crucial to define and actively engage in a participative design process for missions. Within the ECIV project, this necessitates the creation of a safe and trusting space where diverse participants can collaborate. Given the varied backgrounds, perspectives, and expertise within the consortium, fostering a sense of psychological safety is paramount. This requires dedicated time and resources for in-person meetings and on-site collaboration, enabling participants to build trust, share ideas openly, and engage in the creative and innovative thinking necessary to achieve the project’s ambitious goals. Only through the deliberate cultivation of such an environment can we unlock the full potential of mission-oriented innovation and drive meaningful change. In direct support of this principle, a two-day on-site design workshop was conducted during ECIV’s consortium meeting in Borlänge, Sweden, providing a dedicated space for collaborative design and innovation.

ECIV partners participating in the workshops on the 25th and 26th of March in Borlänge, Sweden

Define shared transformational goals

ECIV’s overall mission of transformation to a European circular economy eco-system is ambitious but not achievable within the timeframe of the ECIV project. The overall mission will give the project a direction, but as it will still be abstract in relation to the project timeline it can be difficult to direct the work within the project as it implies mobilizing actors and coordinate a portfolio of actions and tools that go beyond the project timeline. The project has therefore defined a set of sub-missions with a deadline that aligns with the project deadline and work as steppingstones towards the overall mission. Giving the project clear transformational goals that are achievable within the project timeframe.

The ECIV project works over three horizons of change (figure 7). The regional and

interregional analysis has given an understanding of the current system and the conditions that manifest this state (A). The sub-missions will support enablers (B) and opportunities (C) in the transition zone as the conditions of the future system develops.

Three horizons of change

Figure 7. Three horizons of change. (Source: Sharp et al, (2016) *Three horizons: a pathway practice for transformation*)

To have a shared vision of what future the sub-missions should aim to contribute towards, a desired future scenario describing the future system with a European circular economy eco-system and its' effects in 2050 was introduced. The scenario was described based on the overall EVIC mission and the shared focus areas identified in the interregional analysis of the circular economy system.

With this share vision of what a European circular economy eco system entails and what values it would create, as a base, sub-missions were developed and defined.

In a co-workshop regional representatives were first tasked to describe desired futures for the year 2029 given the speculative narrative of the future in the year 2029. What does the future look like in 2029 if the transformation should reach the speculative scenario by 2050. After this a set of sub-missions were formulated based on the scenarios and the understanding and knowledge of the current system. The sub-missions describe measurable transformational goals for 2029, that would engage actors from multiple sectors and drive the overall transformation towards the 2050 scenario.

Lastly, the regional participants reviewed and iterated the sub-missions to ensure they were relevant given the desired future and the identified challenges, had a concrete goal that would be achievable and possible to follow up on by 2029. The missions were also reviewed based on their potential to engage actors across various sectors.

A check list reviewing and refining the Sub-missions

Legitimacy

- Is this relevant for the ECIV regions' stakeholders? Would it engage the stakeholders?
- What sectors/themes in the ECIV eco-system does the mission involve?

Goal formulation /ambition Level

- Is it a relevant goal?
- Is the goal feasible by 2029?
- Is the goal ambitious enough?

Figure 8. Checklist used for Sub-mission design. (Source: Wittmann, F.; Hummler, A.; Posch, D.; Lindner, R. (2024): Missions with Impact: A practical guide to formulating effective missions. Bertelsmann Stiftung, Sustainable Social Market Economies, Gütersloh. <https://doi.org/10.11586/2024078>)

Figure 9. ECIV Circular Ecosystem Design. ECIV, WP2.

ECIV Sub-missions: Top-down proposals

Workshop results 25th and 26th March 2025:

- 1a - By 2029 the level of industrial symbiosis should have increased by X % from starting point.
- 1b - By 2029 every region has identified or developed at least 3 new opportunities for industrial symbiosis.
- 2 - By 2029 "to design out waste" is an integrated policy in all ECIV Regional action plans.
- 3a - By 2029 the extraction and import of virgin raw materials should be decreased by X% from starting point.
- 3b - By 2029 the use of secondary raw materials should be increased by X% from starting point.
- 4 - By 2029 X% of products manufactured in the region should be based on product-as-a-service business models.
- 5 - Agrofood systems or Food production should have reduced waste by X% from the start-point by 2029.
- 6 - Circular metals and minerals should have increased the reuse of critical strategic materials in EU by X% from starting point by 2029.
- 7a - In 2029 packaging should be X% circular (or 100% circular in 2040)
- 7b - In 2029 packaging in food production and consumption should be 100% circular
- 8 - By 2029, the use of biobased materials in construction (or building?) should have increased by X% from starting point.
- 9a - By 2029 Valorisation of by-products should have increased by X% from starting point.
- 9b - Increased Valorisation of by-products from steel production by x% from starting point by 2029.
- 10 - By 2029 the use of fresh water in industrial processes should be reduced by X% in ECIV regions.
- 11 - In 2029 waste from textile production will be reduced by X% from starting point.
- 12 - In 2029 we have developed net innovative Electric & Electronic waste processes for an efficient to reuse, reduce, recycle, refurbish, repair-replicable at local scale.
- 13 - In 2029 revenues from circular business has increased by X% from starting point.

The sub-missions will be further iterated and detailed in collaboration with work package three, where stakeholders and other actors within the system will be mobilized to discuss the ambition and goals of the missions in a bottom-up approach. This will be done both to ensure the final missions are engaging and to develop a sense of co-ownership of the defined direction.

The ECIV project leverages a combined top-down and bottom-up approach to mission design, ensuring both strategic alignment and practical relevance. The process begins with the top-down formulation of sub-missions, drawing upon academic research and the collective experiences of the participating regions. These initial sub-missions are then validated and refined through extensive stakeholder engagement, actively involving Quadruple Helix actors.

This bottom-up process results in an interregional missions-oriented innovation program (TIP) and regional action plans that are directly responsive to the needs and capabilities of local stakeholders. This integrated approach is crucial for ensuring that the missions are not only grounded in research and strategic priorities but also are effectively tailored for implementation and impact within the diverse regional contexts of the ECIV project. By combining these perspectives, ECIV maximizes the potential for achieving transformative change and fostering a truly circular economy.

Based on the defined sub-missions the ECIV project will create and coordinate a portfolio of actions and tools to achieve the goals of each sub-mission. This will both be done through calls for projects as well as regional actions to, for example, develop and maintain structures enabling stakeholder mobilization and engagement.

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Appendix 1

Conditions for Circular Economy in ECIV Regions – Self Assessment

Survey, SWOT-analysis and Regional
stakeholder workshops results

Dalarna/NMS in collaboration with WSP, with
contributions from all ECIV regions

2025-03-20

Contents

The purpose of this report is to show, and discuss, results from the Survey, SWOT-analysis, and Regional Workshops investigating conditions for circular economy in the nine regions participating in ECIV.

- **Focus:** Identifying synergies/patterns between regions, and highlighting observations in need of further information/discussion

p. 3 – Policies, Incentives and Strategies

p. 7 – Funding Opportunities

p. 10 – Sectors, Resource Flows, Industries, and Waste

p. 17 – Platforms, Programs, Projects, and Networks

p. 20 – Local Stories: SWOT Analysis

p. 28 – Stakeholder Workshop Results

Policies, Incentives, and Strategies

The following slides summarize results from the survey regarding

- Relevant policies (and strategies), their objectives and incentives related to circular economy
- Specific targets and the activities for reaching those targets

Point of Departure

Policies, incentives, and strategies are mentioned interchangeably across regional surveys. Strategies are mentioned more than (international, national, regional, or local) policies and incentives.

Observations have been compiled and are presented together. However, there are some distinctions between them.

Policies, Incentives, and Strategies

- **Regulatory Policies and Incentives** are highlighted by 6 regions (Normandy, North Middle Sweden, Lithuania, Scotland, Northern Netherlands, Helsinki-Uusimaa) – including laws, bills, rules and regulations
- **Financial Incentives** are highlighted by 5 regions (North Middle Sweden, Lithuania, Normandy, Scotland, and Helsinki-Uusimaa) – including grants, loans, tax incentives, and incentive pricing (for household waste collection)
- **Other Incentives** that are highlighted include public campaigns and initiatives, student and employee training, and strategic projects
- **Specific Strategies/Agendas for Circular Economy** have been developed in 7 regions (Navarra, Normandy, Gabrovo, Scotland, Wallonia, Northern Netherlands, Lithuania)
- **Objectives for Circular Economy are Integrated in Several Strategies** in many regions, e.g. regional planning and development, waste prevention, water management, smart specialization, innovation, energy and climate

- **Examples of National laws and bills:** Scotland's Circular Economy Bill, France's Anti-waste and Circular Economy Law, Spain's Anti-waste law for a circular economy
- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)** is highlighted by 3 regions (North Middle Sweden, Normandy, and Scotland) – which focuses on action and accountability across entire product lifecycles
- **Green/Sustainable/Circular Public Procurement** is highlighted by 3 regions (Navarra, North Middle Sweden, and Scotland)

Targets and Activities

- **Targets and Activities** are region specific and developed in more detail in the surveys (→ and strategies)

- **Common Themes – Targets:**

- *Decreasing raw material/natural resource use* (Navarra, Gabrovo, Helsinki-Uusima, Northern Netherlands)
- *Increasing waste recovery/Waste management* (Navarra, Gabrovo, Lithuania, Helsinki-Uusima)
- *Industry/business development* (all regions)
- *Innovation and research* (North Middle Sweden, Wallonia, Lithuania)
- *Stakeholder engagement and coordination* (Navarra, North Middle Sweden, Normandy)

- **Common Themes – Activities:**

- Promoting sustainable consumption, regulation
- Improving infrastructure (recycling etc.), promotion and communication, regulation
- Circular business models, funding programs, support for startups, education and training
- Research funding, test beds, platforms, networks
- PPPs, value-chain-cooperation, promotion and communication

Funding Opportunities

The following slides summarize results from the survey regarding financing and funding opportunities for the transition to the circular economy that are available in the regions.

Point of Departure

The survey results show that there are many funding opportunities available within the regions. In the next slide, regional answers have been mapped to show the variety of funding opportunities. Some overarching observations are presented to the right.

Synergies

- **EU initiatives:** several regions highlight european and EU initiatives, e.g. ERDF, Horizon, LIFE
- **governments:** all regions highlight government support (local, regional, national)
- **private sector:** several regions highlight support through e.g. green loans/bonds, venture capital

Other observations

- **differences in compilation:** it's likely several regions could complete their answers with more funding opportunities (e.g. EU-level)

Funding Opportunities

Navarra	North Middle Sweden	Normandy	Gabrovo	Scotland	Wallonia	Lithuania	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Northern Netherlands
Regional Government of Navarra (competitive regional calls for R&D projects focused on circular economy, tax incentives, aids, waste fund grants)	Region Gävleborg (support for SMEs, assessment tool for sustainable project funding)	Regional Council of Normandy & Economic Development Agency of Normandy (IDEE Action programs, ERDF support, various funds and schemes)	Support for startups: Horizon Europe, LIFE, regional initiatives with local entities for co-financing and mentorship, Public-Private Partnerships for funding and scaling startups	Circular Economy Business Support Service (consultancy, advice, funding)	Financial tools: EasyGreen loans, Chèques Economie Circulaire, and NEXT customized financing. Public aids and network of circular economy experts.	Invega (financial assistance for business development and targeted projects)	European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and European Social Fund (ESF), Competitive calls – EU, Interreg, Horizon, Leader	NNLs regional ERDF 2021–2027 programme , with circular economy as one of the four priority areas. Plus, cofunding through Ministry of Economic Affairs
	Almi (green loans, verification fund, venture capital)							
	Tregion Startup Invest (investment company for businesses withing incubators in NMS)	ADEME (twenty schemes dedicated to circular economy support)	EU funding mechanisms: Horizon Europe, ERDF, Just Transition Fund, and LIFE Programme	Investment fund for Scotland (commercial finance options for smaller businesses)	Regional Call for Projects: Go Circular and specific calls for the construction sector	Environmental Projects Management Agency (climate change program and decarbonisation scheme)		
National Ministry of the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge	Naturvårdsverket (The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, investment support through Klimatklivet)	Circular Economy Fund – ORMAT (financial support for sorting and preparation of waste for recycling etc.)	National funding sources: National Trust EcoFund and Innovation Fund Bulgaria	Support for Innovation R&D <i>(guide to support for innovation, R&D by Scottish Government and UK Government)</i>	Supporting Innovation: Call for circular projects, Financing digital solutions, Encouraging circular design		Business Finland	National Programme Groningen for province of Groningen, transformation due to ending of natural gas production
	EU funds, ERDF	BPI (public investment bank, schemes dedicated to transition projects)	Regional and local opportunities: Gabrovo Municipality Development Programs, PPPs		EU and international programs: e.g. Horizon, LIFE		Cities’ own funding program like Helsinki Innovation Fund and Porvoo Climate Fund	EU 2023–2027 rural development programme for NNLs
			Private sector: Green bonds, venture capital		Regional actor AWEX (enhancing european/international visibility)			‘Waddenfonds’ : nationally funded programme for coastal areas and islands, main focus sustainability

Sectors, Resource Flows, Industries & Waste

The following slides summarize results from the survey regarding:

- Prioritized sectors and industries
- Prioritized resource flows
- Industries with largest turnovers
- Industries with largest volumes of residual resources
- Biggest volumes of waste

Point of Departure

The results show that there are many similarities among the regions. There are also detectable differences, reflecting the diverse set of industries driving regional economies.

In the following slides, regional answers have been mapped and synergies among regions have been identified. Some overarching observations are presented to the right.

Synergies

- **sectors and industries:** construction, plastics, energy, food and agriculture
- **resource flows:** plastics, steel and metal, construction materials, and textiles
- **turnovers:** manufacturing, transport/automotive, agrifood, construction, ICT
- **residual resources:** manufacturing, food, and construction
- **waste volumes:** household waste, construction waste, paper waste, and industrial waste

Other observations

- **industrial base:** regions with strong industrial bases prioritize residues from their key industries (e.g., steel and forest industry in North Middle Sweden)
- **data presentation (and access?):** variations in categorization, quantitative estimations, level of detail etc.

Prioritized resource flows

Navarra	North Middle Sweden	Normandy	Gabrovo	Scotland	Wallonia	Lithuania	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Northern Netherlands
Steel	Residual heat from pulp and paper mill industries, data centers	Plastics	Metals and metal products for machine building and tool manufacturing	Plastics	Construction and buildings	Construction waste	Food	Urban mining materials like minerals, metals , woods, and material comp.
Plastics	Bio-raw materials from sawmills	Agricultural biomass	Plastics for various industrial applications	Food and Organics	Water	Plastics	Construction	Municipal waste like packaging, plastics , organic residues, textiles
Recycled aggregates	Residues from the paper and pulp industry	Non-metallic minerals	Electricity and natural gas	Textiles	Metallurgy and batteries	Metal ores and products	Plastics	Agrifood: biobased materials to be used as raw material for biobased plastics, textiles, construction materials
Plastic waste mix	Residues from the forest industry	Agricultural and aquatic biomass	Water resources	Electronics (E-waste)	Food industry and food systems	Fossil fuels and by-products	Textiles	
Light fragmentation residues	Construction waste	Wood and wood products		Metals (including critical raw materials)	Textiles	Electronic waste	E-waste	
Road milling	Residues from the steel industry	Metal ores and products		Construction and Demolition Waste	Plastics	Chemicals		Metals and critical raw materials
Construction waste	Residues from mining waste	Non-metallic minerals and products		Glass	Biobased economy			
	Furniture, textiles	Fossil fuels and by-products						
	Residues from coffee production	Linen						

Industries with largest volumes of residual resources

Navarra	North Middle Sweden	Normandy	Gabrovo	Scotland	Wallonia	Lithuania	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Northern Netherlands
<p><i>Hazardous waste:</i> Vehicle manufacturing, manufacturing of metal products, vehicle repair workshops, metallurgy. Common waste types: chemical waste, industrial effluent sludge, oil.</p>	<p>Forest industry: residual products, branches and crowns (GROT), sawdust, chips, bark, chemical pulp</p>	Petrochemicals	<p>Manufacturing industries: metal shavings and scrap, plastic offcuts, textile scraps</p>	<p>Whiskey sector co-products: draff, pot ale, spent lees/wash, pot ale syrup, distillers dark grain</p>	<p>Steel and metallurgical industry: slag, furnace dust, metallurgical sludge</p>	<p>Manufacturing: mineral waste, black metal waste</p>	<p>Surplus land masses and asphalt from infra</p>	<p>Construction industry -> residual materials wood, packaging, concrete, minerals, metals, glass, etc.</p>
		Pharmaceuticals	<p>Food industry: organic waste, packaging materials</p>	<p>Cheese making: over 500,000 tonnes of material available</p>	<p>Construction: construction and demolition waste</p>	<p>Construction: mineral construction waste, black metal</p>	<p>Ashes from energy production</p>	<p>Chemical -> residuals are CO2 and heat</p>
	<p><i>Non-hazardous waste:</i> Metallurgy, manufacturing of metal products, manufacturing of vehicles, waste collection and treatment sector. Common waste types: ferrous metal waste, other mineral residues, animal and plant waste, paper and cardboard waste.</p>		<p>Food processing</p>		<p>Waste water sludge</p>	<p>Chemical industry: spent solvents, chemical by-products, plastic waste</p>		<p>Concrete, tiles, metals, and wood from construction</p>
		Energy		<p>Animal and mixed food waste</p>	<p>Agri-food industry: organic residues</p>		<p>Industrial sidestreams from chemical and plastics industries</p>	<p>Energy -> heat and CO2</p>
		Glass		<p>Farm slurry and manure arisings</p>	<p>Paper and cardboard industry: papermaking sludge, trimming waste</p>		<p>Forest: bark, sawdust, wood chips, black liquor, green liquor</p>	<p>Metal and manufacturing -> metal, heat, CO2</p>
		Waste management					<p>Agribio: crop residues, manure, sludge, food processing by-products</p>	<p>Agriculture and agrifood industry -> organic residues, nutrients, greenhouse gases</p>

Biggest volumes of waste

Navarra	North Middle Sweden	Normandy	Gabrovo	Scotland	Wallonia	Lithuania	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Northern Netherlands
Hazardous waste: 38,595 tons	Household waste: residual waste, food waste, packaging waste	Inert construction waste	Industrial waste: metal, plastics	Soils	Household waste	Recyclables	General waste	Main source that still end-up in the furnace: Organic residues, household
Non-hazardous waste: 834,907 tons	Construction and demolition waste: concrete and bricks, waste from construction and demolition, wood waste, scrap metal	Plastic	Municipal solid waste: household waste , including organics, plastics, paper , and glass	Household waste	Construction and demolition waste	Construction and demolishing	Bio waste	construction materials, textiles, metals, sludge and digestate, and dipers
		Textiles		Mineral waste from construction and demolition	Industrial waste	Domestic	Paper waste	
	Industrial waste: production waste, hazardous waste	Hazardous waste		Vegetal waste	Organic waste	Dark metal	WEEE	Main sources that are being recycled: Paper and cardboard, plastics and plastic packaging, glass, etc.
	Electronic waste: electronic devices, batteries and accumulators	Metals, glass, paper , cardboard		Mixed and undifferentiated materials	Electronic waste	Mineral waste	Wood waste	
				Animal and mixed food waste		Paper	Plastic waste	Composting and fermentation
				Wood waste		Waste treatment residues	Cardboard waste	
				Common sludges			Metal waste	
				Animal faeces, urine and manure			Glass waste	

Platforms, Programs, Projects, and Networks

The following slides summarize results from the survey regarding platforms, (research)-programs, (research)-projects and networks:

- A. That are already working with circular economy and/or innovation
- B. That engage relevant stakeholders for creating circular economy

Point of Departure

There is significant variation in compilation across regions. Some regions provide short lists, others offer longer lists, and some include extensive descriptions. The format also varies, with some regions categorizing answers into groups A and B and/or the quadruple helix, while others do not.

The initial compilation of stakeholders represents a preliminary list. Future work within ECIV will further deepen the analysis.

Synergies

- **many platforms, programs, projects, and networks:** highlighted by majority of regions
- **categories:** detectable categories of platforms, projects, programs and networks include *academic/research institutions, governments, PPPs, innovation and technology* (e.g. hubs, clusters)

Other observations

- **differences in compilation:** it's likely several regions could complete their answers with more platforms, projects etc.

Navarra	North Middle Sweden	Normandy	Gabrovo	Scotland	Wallonia	Lithuania	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Northern Netherlands	
Navarra Zirkular: a public private hub on circular economy supporting industrial transition. Promoted by multiple departments and public companies.	Byggdialog Dalarna, Dalarna Science Park, University of Dalarna, Sustainable Steel Region, and IUC Dalarna	Agri-Food: Engineering schools, industrial chairs, labcoms, and projects like Ag & Food City Lab, and Experimental Farm	Gabrovo Municipality	UK Innovate - Launchpad	Wallonia describes that there are various groups and councils to ensure effective implementation of the circular economy strategy. Including coordination units, steering committees, councils, platforms, taskforces, and thematic working groups	Government: Ministries of Environment, Economy and Innovation, Agriculture, as well as Innovation Agency (GreenTech Hub group), Environmental Projects Management Agency, and Municipalities	Helsinki-Uusimaa describes that in addition to Circular Hub, there are more than 100 projects, research programmes, networks and platforms operating in the region.	Circular Groningen (network/cluster)	
			Regional Innovation Center "Ambitious Gabrovo"	IbioIC (Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre)				Circular Friesland (network/cluster)	
	Technical University of Gabrovo	Bioeconomy Cluster Builder	Greenwise Campus (platform)						
	Miljöforum, RISE, University of Gävle, Movexum, Propell, Sandbacka Science Park, Swedish Metals & Minerals, and Voxkedjan	Industrial: ECTOTECHNILIN, NATUREPLAST, DEPESTELE, ACTALIA	Technical University of Gabrovo	Bioeconomy Cluster Builder		Industry: Circular Economy Cluster, Clean Tech Cluster, and various recycling and waste management companies as well as companies using circular practices and looking for new solutions and innovations		They highlight Closed Plastic Circle – from Pilots into, SPIRIT programme, Helsinki Circular Economy Cluster Program	SUSPAC (network)
	Energy: Industrial chairs, engineering schools, graduate schools, EUR MATENGY and labex centers	B: Businesses (Mechatronica SC, Impuls SC, Senstate Technologies SC, Tehnoles Ltd, Scientia, Elna Ltd, STS Electronics Ltd, Adtech Ltd, Acronis, Unitraf JSC, EmCB Ltd, Pastili Ltd), Gabrovo District Administration, and Gabrovo Chamber of Commerce and Industry	ECIV	Community: NGO Circular Economy, Environmental Coalition, Lithuania's Consumers Alliance, and Lithuania's Innovation Center					Relevant stakeholders include Clic Innovation, VTT, Business Finland Veturi programs, University of Helsinki, Aalto University, Posintra, Forum Virium, Business Helsinki, Haaga-Helia
	Paper Province, Karlstad University, Glava Energy Center, CircLab, LignoCity, and various research projects and networks	Construction: engineering schools, industrial chairs				University of Applied Sciences, Laurea University of Applied Sciences, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, cities and municipalities	Circular Drenthe (to be launched in 2025) – network/cluster		
		Automotive: Cléon 4.0 electric mobility cluster and partnership Faurecia					Northern Innovation Lab Circular Economy – NICE (platform)		
	Gävle Energi, Gästrike Återvinnare, Gävleborg Chamber of Commerce, CirEko, Cradlenet	Chemistry: EUR XL-Chem, Carnot I2C, and various labs and projects							
		Others: ARKEMA, Ecole de Management de Normandie, Normandy IPCC, Le Dôme					Others: Miesto Laboratorija		
		B: CREC (Regional Committee of Circular Economy), Labo NECI, NEODD, SYNAPSE, Le Hangar Zéro, and more							

Local Stories: SWOT Analysis

The following slides summarize results from the survey regarding the SWOT analyses for regional conditions for the transition to the circular economy. This includes:

- Strengths
- Weaknesses
- Opportunities
- Threats

Point of Departure

The results from the SWOT analysis clarify, confirm, and elaborate on local conditions for the circular economy. The SWOT analysis also makes it easier to identify patterns across different regions.

While not all regions experience the same conditions, many share commonalities. There are also differences. For example, one region's strength can be another region's weakness.

Strengths

- **Government/Institutional Support** – emphasized by majority of regions
- **Collaboration** (e.g. networks, platforms, diverse actors in different sectors) – emphasized by all regions
- **Innovation and R&D** – emphasized by majority all regions
- **Circular Economy Strategies** – emphasized by Navarra, Normandy, and Wallonia
- **Resources and Infrastructure** (e.g. raw material, recycling infra.) – emphasized by Lithuania, Helsinki-Uusimaa, North Middle Sweden, and Scotland

Weaknesses

- **Budget Constraints / Uncertainties** – emphasized by Normandy, Wallonia, Helsinki-Uusimaa, Gabrovo, and Scotland
- **Lack of Coordination / “Fragmented Facilitating Ecosystem”** – emphasized by Navarra, Wallonia, and Northern Netherlands
- **Skills and Workforce** (e.g. talent shortages, low gender equality, negative net migration and low attractiveness) – emphasized by Navarra, North Middle Sweden, and Normandy
- **Regulatory and Policy Gaps** – emphasized by Lithuania, Helsinki-Uusimaa, North Middle Sweden, and Normandy

Strenghts

Navarra

- Regional commitment
 - PPP: Navarra Zirkular
- Circular economy strategy
 - Public subsidies
- Industrial and innovative region
 - Institutional support
- Collaboration with universities

Lithuania

- Awareness between companies, policymakers, academia
- Collaboration between business and science
 - Tech-driven economy
- Participation in EU-projects
- Recycling infrastructure

Helsinki-Uusimaa

- Critical mass: population (1.7 m), infrastructure, logistics hub, material flows, business density, data
- Strong actors: R&D, funders, ministries, HQ, companies, cities
- Strong sectors and key clusters
 - Ambitious goals

North Middle Sweden

- Natural resources, particularly forests, and high renewable energy usage
- Test beds and innovation systems
- Collaboration between business, industry, public access, academia, as well as international networks

Normandy

- Circular economy strategy
- Waste management plan
- Internal coordination between departments/strategies
- Governance steer strategy: region, ADEME, French government
 - Clubs and networks
- Financial support, and skills

Northern Netherlands

- Circular economy clusters
- Cross-regional collaboration
- SME region, pragmatic oriented
 - Strong sectors
- High level of expertise, frontrunner
 - Community commitment
- Policy and policy instruments
 - Education and knowledge

Wallonia

- Expertise circular innovation
- Circular economy strategy
 - Innovation strategy
- Waste management strategy
- Ecosystem of actors, stakeholders
 - Governance within strategies
 - Mapping regional projects, stakeholders, trends

Gabrovo

- Industrialized region with developed business infrastructure
- Development of ICT sector
 - Institutional awareness
- Administration supporting entrepreneurship
 - Technical university

Scotland

- Research excellence (institutions and skilled workforce)
 - Government support
- Innovation and collaboration
 - Sustainable resources
- Small well connected place which aids collaboration

Weaknesses

Navarra

- Shortage qualified talent
- Lack of coordination/collaboration between sectors
 - Insufficient material flow/traceability
- Complex logistics in value chains
- Absence regional data/indicators

Lithuania

- Linear models still cheaper and more accessible
- Stakeholder motivation lacks
 - Lack of regulation
 - Lack of public pressure and awareness
- Lack of recycling, recover capacity

Helsinki-Uusimaa

- Silos in municipalities and cities
- Poor municipal financial situations
- No network for circular economy
 - "Information is not circulating"
 - High costs industrial land
- Waste pricing (against recycling)
- Lack of sales and branding skills

North Middle Sweden

- Involving SMEs in transition
- Procurement constraints
- Developing demonstration projects
- High energy consumption and emissions from transport
- Demographics: skilled workforce, net migration, gender

Normandy

- Budget cuts
- Difficulties finding relevant measures and indicators
- S3 Strategy insufficiently aligned with regional policies
 - Small workforce
 - Lack of regulatory powers

Northern Netherlands

- Multiple clusters and networks working parallel – fragmented facilitating ecosystem

Wallonia

- Budget uncertainty
- Lack of experience regional actors in european projects
- Difficulty internal collaboration, lack of synergies between strategies
 - Lack of knowledge
- Difficulty involving new actors

Gabrovo

- Insufficient capacity to apply modern digital technologies
- Limited access to know-how
- Low interactions bussiness-universities
- Low community awareness
- Low R&D intensity/productivity
- Limited financial resources

Scotland

- Systemic challenges affecting businesses, e.g. lack of shared understanding and language
- Public sector budgets & political change
 - Funding gaps
 - Market penetration
- Tied up waste streams / Feedstock competition

Opportunities

- **Competitiveness** (e.g. new markets and exports, industry transformation, pilot platforms, new business models) – emphasized majority of regions
- **Collaboration** (e.g. ECIV, extending PPPs) – emphasized by majority of regions
- **European Initiatives** (e.g. Green Deal, CRM act, project calls) – emphasized by Normandy, Wallonia, Lithuania, Helsinki-Uusimaa, and Northern Netherlands
- **Expertise and Skills** (e.g. employment generation, increasing attractiveness, CE study programs) – emphasized by Navarra, North Middle Sweden, Northern Netherlands, and Scotland

Threats

- **Regulatory and Policy Barriers** – emphasized by Navarra, Lithuania, Helsinki-Uusimaa, Northern Netherlands, and Wallonia
- **Economic and Political Uncertainty** – emphasized by Lithuania, North Middle Sweden, and Scotland
- **Dependence on Imports** – emphasized by Lithuania, Normandy, Wallonia, and Gabrovo
- **Climate Change** – emphasized by North Middle Sweden, and Scotland

Opportunities

Navarra

- Extended collaboration, e.g. ECIV, across sectors, interterritorial, knowledge sharing
- New funding opportunities
- Employment generation
- Industrial transformation
- Business model development

Lithuania

- EU Green deal
 - ECIV
- Synergies with decarbonisation, sustainability activities
- New markets, export possibilities
 - New R&D opportunities

Helsinki-Uusimaa

- Pilot platforms
- Co-development through PPPs
 - Public procurement
 - Green deal
 - New industries
 - Land use planning
 - Digitalization
 - Branding

North Middle Sweden

- Focused measures smart specialization
 - PPPs, e.g. procurement
- Network of test beds (bioeconomy)
- Developments in forest, construction and steel industries
 - Circular value chains & models
 - R&I environments
 - Conditions for attracting best skills

Normandy

- Industrial region with potential impact from ECIV
 - National calls targeting Normandy
 - Observatory with growing expertise
- The Green deal, European calls, Preparatory action
- More organisations show interest

Northern Netherlands

- Circular economy priority in regional, cross regional and national policies
- Raw material transition
- Less netcongestion and less space limitation for circular industries
 - CE might decrease unemployment

Wallonia

- European trends/obligations (CRM act, NZIA, ...)
- New government – support
- ECIV collaboration, and other interregional strategic partnerships
- Studies within circular strategy could increase collaboration

Gabrovo

- Industry (and public sector) development through digitalization
 - New image for the region
- International networks/projects
- Creating successful examples R&D
 - Foreign investors
- Business dynamics in knowledge-based sectors
- Plastic field interested in circular ec.

Scotland

- Economic growth (new markets, productivity, savings)
 - Global leadership (position Scotland as leader in bioeconomy and circular economy)
 - Job creation
 - Sustainability goals

Threats

Navarra

- Regulatory constraints
- Costs and profits compared to linear products/solutions
- Insufficient coordination among stakeholders
- Lack of uniformity in how circular practices are managed

Lithuania

- Unstable geopolitical situation
- Dependence on material imports
 - Growing demand for new products
- Lack of technologies; lack of efficient ways of recycling

Helsinki-Uusimaa

- Slow operational culture
- Small actors not included
 - Activities do not scale up/replicate
- Low profits circular solutions
 - Lack of shared vision/commitment
 - Lack of skilled labor
 - Regulatory barriers

North Middle Sweden

- Climate change hampers development of forest production
- Lack of awareness/skills to handle barter (incl. balancing climate-related, social, economic goals)
- Slow political development at national and international level regarding low-carbon economy

Normandy

- Few research organizations involved in circular economy
- Scarcity of resources, sectors under pressure
- Dependence on imports for certain materials

Northern Netherlands

- Virgin materials cheaper
- Taxes and increasing loans make refurbishment and repair expensive
- Electricity grid congestion, permit limitation, and space limitations
- EU and national regulations still based on linear systems

Wallonia

- Costs and lack of labor in certain sectors
- Non-economically-viable circular solutions
- "Circularity as a threat" to some sectors (e.g. single use plastics)
 - Regulatory barriers
 - Dependence on imports

Gabrovo

- Demographic challenges, e.g. ageing workforce, migration
 - Lack of skilled workers, entrepreneurs, scientific capacity
- Low interest community actors
- Lack of funding opportunities at local level
 - Dependency on import

Scotland

- Climate crisis
- Global competition
- Economic uncertainty
- Resistance to change

Stakeholder Workshop Results

The following slides summarize results from the stakeholder workshops. Results are presented combined and by region.

Point of Departure

Eight of the nine participating ECIV regions conducted stakeholder workshops to validate and expand upon the initial circular economy analysis. These workshops aimed to engage regional stakeholders in a discussion of identified challenges and opportunities, exploring local capabilities and resources to address them.

A key objective was to gather input for the design of potential sub-missions, ensuring alignment with regional priorities and expertise. The workshops provided valuable insights into regional capabilities, informing the subsequent top-down sub-mission formulation process.

While WP2 provided a general framework for workshop structure, each region adapted the format and methodologies to best suit their specific conditions and contexts, employing diverse approaches.

Questions

- Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- Did the stakeholders recognize the identified challenges and opportunities?
- What were the reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis?
- Was there anything the stakeholders felt was missing in the analysis?
- Was there anything in the analysis that surprised any of the stakeholders?
- What do the stakeholders feel is most interesting?

- Reflection 2: Capabilities

- What capabilities do the stakeholders believe will be needed moving forward in the region? (e.g. skills, resources, support)
- What capabilities do the stakeholders believe will be needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region?
- Are these capabilities available among the stakeholders?
- Do the stakeholders feel ownership/have ability to take ownership?
- Are there any capabilities that need to be developed further in the region?

Main Take Aways

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- **Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:**
 - The majority of stakeholders recognized identified challenges and opportunities.
 - *Common challenges:* Lack of awareness and knowledge; Financial constraints; Regulatory and policy barriers; Collaboration and networking issues; Technological and infrastructure challenges
 - *Common opportunities:* Public procurement; Innovation ecosystems and collaboration; Development of circular business models; Policy and regulatory support; Education and workforce development
- **Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:**
 - Differing reactions among regional stakeholders. Overall indication of the analysis being too broad/surface level, and a need for more detailed information.
 - Some stakeholders felt detached from the analysis due to a lack of clear purpose and practical applications. Concerns about the robustness and representativeness of the methodology were raised.
 - Some stakeholders showed interest in the fact that other regions share similar potential circular challenges.

- **Missing aspects in the analysis:**
 - *Specificity and Detail:* Sectoral data/challenges/opportunities: Regional economic structures, Connections between impact and dependencies
 - *Policy and Regulatory Information:* At national, regional and EU level; Detailed information barriers
 - *Geopolitical Context:* Geopolitical uncertainties and potential impact on CE
- **Surprising aspects in the analysis:**
 - *Degree of Circularity:* A couple regions were surprised by, and questioned, circularity rates
- **Most interesting aspects in the analysis:**
 - Common interesting aspects include developing practical tools (e.g. CBM), collaborative efforts, sector-specific strengths, and supportive policy frameworks to advance the circular economy across different regions

Main Take Aways

Reflection 2: Capabilities

- **Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:**
 - *Collaboration and Networking:* Between industry, municipalities and research; Cross-sector working groups; Involving stakeholders; Facilitating interconnection between companies
 - *Financial Resources and Support:* For SMEs; Developing new CBMs; Coaching, impact assessment and funding innovation; Funding instruments for high-risk investments
 - *Skills and Knowledge Development:* CA evaluation, design skills, regulatory knowledge, and marketing; Developing a toolbox for companies to create value through circular solutions; Increasing skills and workforce, especially in repair; Education and workforce development for circular economy skills
 - *Regulatory and Policy Incentives:* Need for regulations that encourage circular practices and solutions; Public Procurement
 - *Technical and Infrastructural Support:* Better waste collection and sorting systems; Improving scale-up infrastructure
 - *Market Development:* For recycled materials; Optimizing value chains within the EU context
 - *Consumer Awareness and Behavioral Change*

- **Available capabilities among the stakeholders:**
 - Majority of regions have partially available capabilities in the region, but highlight the need to develop and strengthen them.
 - A few regions have high available capabilities in the region, e.g. through many engaged stakeholders in CE.
 - One region state capabilities are low, with a need to bring professionals from other regions.
- **Stakeholder ownership:**
 - 50/50 among the regions between high and partial ownership among stakeholders.

Helsinki-Uusimaa

Methodology

- **Stakeholder interviews** validating the topics of
 - Regional SWOT
 - ECIV Interregional analyses
 - Sector-specific challenges and opportunities
- **Interviewees** include representatives from Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Hub (General), CLIC Innovation (Plastics/Textiles), STJM (Finnish Textile Industry Association), University of Helsinki (Food), and Political appointee for the ECIV (general)
- **Continuous discussion** with policymakers and funding agencies in Spring 2025

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Challenges: Lack of industrial land and high costs, especially in urban areas like Helsinki. Financial constraints, particularly for SMEs. Lack of networks for circular economy collaboration. Limited incentives for circular business models, especially in waste management and secondary raw materials.
 - Opportunities: Public procurement as a driver for circular economy. Growing innovation ecosystems, such as the 4R Innovation Ecosystem. Support for high-level circular strategies leveraging Finland's strong policy environment. Expansion of repair and reuse business models, especially in textiles and packaging. Caution regarding the challenges in circular construction due to the sector's economic downturn.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Some stakeholders felt detached from the analysis due to a lack of clear purpose and practical applications. Concerns about the robustness and representativeness of the methodology. General themes (e.g., plastics, construction, food) were relevant, but context-specific factors were questioned. The role of circular public procurement was underestimated.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Lack of specificity on strong sectors and the need for referring back to previous studies. Circular economy workforce development was underrepresented. More focus needed on business model innovation and strategic coordination between regions.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - The identification of textiles as a key sector was well-received. Surprised by the lack of emphasis on repair and reuse models. Geopolitical uncertainties and their potential impact on the circular transition were acknowledged but not previously emphasized. Omission of key actors like secondary education institutions and applied research organizations. Concerns over the broad and general nature of the findings.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - Public procurement as a tool for circular transition. Repair and reuse business models in textiles, electronics, and packaging. Collaborative platforms like the 4R Innovation Ecosystem. Finland's potential to lead in high-level circular strategies due to its strong regulatory environment and political will.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Collaboration and networking between industry, municipalities, and research institutions. Financial resources and support mechanisms, particularly for SMEs. Development of circular economy business models, including rental and reuse strategies. Technical and infrastructural support for better waste collection and sorting systems. Regulatory and policy incentives for businesses to transition to circular practices.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - Sector-specific circular strategies for plastics, textiles, and construction. Market development for recycled materials. Public procurement to set standards and push for circular solutions. Education and workforce development for circular economy skills. Consumer awareness and behavioral change through awareness campaigns.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Partially available. Expertise exists within research institutions, industry, and public actors, but there are gaps in funding, infrastructure, and collaboration mechanisms. Strong actors include universities, research institutions (e.g., VTT), and innovation ecosystems (e.g., 4R Innovation Ecosystem). The private sector and SMEs struggle with limited resources.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - Stakeholders acknowledge the importance of regional actors leading by example. Hesitation and risk-aversion among businesses, particularly SMEs, due to financial uncertainty. Lack of cross-sector coordination means no single entity fully owns the circular transition process.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Stronger cross-sector collaboration. Funding instruments for high-risk investments. Scaling up circular solutions beyond pilots and small-scale initiatives. Infrastructure improvements for circular economy activities. Regulatory clarity and support to address barriers like pricing structures for recycled materials.

North Middle Sweden

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including presentations in plenary and discussions in four groups during two sessions:
 - Regional analysis in session 1
 - Interregional analysis in Session 2
 - Printed material in each session with questions related to results from the analyses
 - Group leader in each group
 - Menti to get input on potential icons
 - Total 3,5 hours
- **Attendees** included Funders; Research institute; Universities; Clusters; Lab/testbed; Non profit organization; Science Parks/incubators, accelerators, innovation hubs
 - Funders: Almi, Tregion
 - Research institute: RISE
 - Universities: Högskolan i Dalarna, Högskolan i Gävle, Karlstad Universitet
 - Clusters: Glava Energy Center, Hudiksvalls Hydraulic Cluster, Paper Province, Sustainable Steel Region
 - Lab, testbed: On Demand
 - Non profit organisation: CirEko
 - Science Parks, incubators, acceleratorer, innovation-hubs: EDIH Mighty, Dalarna Science Park, Karlstad Innovation Park, Movexum, Propell, Sandbacka Science Park

North Middle Sweden

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Stakeholders recognized several challenges, including a lack of awareness and knowledge about the circular economy among producers and consumers. The need for skills and governing policies was highlighted as crucial. Challenges include working in silos and cultural norms, particularly the "utility mentality" in NMS. Opportunities include attracting new talent to the region and connecting universities with industries.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Stakeholders found the collaboration opportunities in ECIV interesting and saw funding and European contacts as motivating factors. There was difficulty in understanding the different levels of detail in each region's analysis. Some stakeholders questioned why industrial companies were not included in the workshop.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Stakeholders felt a clearer connection between impact and dependencies was needed. More information on policies, regulations, and incentives, particularly EU regulations, was missing. The analysis lacked a focus on certain resource flows and sectors, such as mining waste, construction, and water issues. Leadership and economic incentives were emphasized as important.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - Stakeholders were surprised by the low degree of circularity in Sweden, with some doubting the accuracy of the 3.4% circular economy figure.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - Policies and incentives were seen as crucial. The potential for start-ups to enter big industries and the importance of human commitment and knowledge were highlighted. Mapping residual flows and creating new business opportunities were seen as challenging but important. Learning from other regions and clusters was considered valuable.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Inspiration and learning from other countries' strategies in circular economy. Connecting circular thinking to the current situation and future goals. Developing a toolbox for companies to create value through circular solutions.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - Same as above, with a focus on circular economy.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Some ongoing projects in NMS, such as collaborations in the forest-based bioeconomy and the agro sector, indicate existing capabilities. Examples include innovation sprints and hackathons with energy-intensive industries.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - This question was not discussed during the workshop.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Common awareness and knowledge about circular design and business models. Capacity to build diverse teams, testbeds, clear strategies, and leadership driving incentives.

Lithuania

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including
 - Presentations of ECIV project and analysis (Priority sectors, turnovers, resource flows, SWOT), circularity rate metrics, and consortium prioritized sectors
 - Group discussions in smaller groups
- **Attendees** included Public Sector; Businesses, associations; Non-governmental sector; Universities
 - 15 participants in total
 - Public sector: Parliament of the Republic of Lithuania, Research Council of Lithuania, Invest Lithuania
 - Businesses, associations: Furniture business, e-waste recycling company, waste managers, packaging design agency, engineering businesses association
 - Non-governmental sector: Educational NVO, Innovation Center of Lithuania

Lithuania

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Stakeholders partly recognized the challenges and opportunities but questioned the quality of existing data and the statements' origins. The lack of education and awareness about circularity was identified as a significant challenge. Another challenge was the lack of clear practical guidelines on the EU's new directives and policies. Opportunities included innovations for secondary raw material usage and encouraging product designs that fit circularity criteria.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Participants mainly focused on analyzing Lithuanian sectors and market but emphasized the importance of collaborating with other regions due to Lithuania's small market for secondary raw materials. There were questions about the definitions of sectors, such as plastics.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Stakeholders wanted more explanation on the methodology and data sources. Suggested additions included challenges of CO2 emissions calculations, LCA incorporation, regulatory barriers, deeper analysis of technological challenges, and specific sector data.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - Stakeholders were surprised that higher awareness was considered a strength. They were also surprised by Lithuania's low position in the EU circularity rate and questioned the methodology.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - Concepts like assembly/disassembly, regulations, policy frameworks, early preparation for regulations, lack of financing, design thinking, international partnerships, and mono-materials were highlighted as interesting.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Capabilities needed include LCA evaluation, topical knowledge for funding calls, design skills, holistic and interdisciplinary knowledge, regulatory knowledge, standardization, marketing, entrepreneurship, and circular economy concepts.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - Same as above, with a focus on circular economy.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Fragmented, sectorial knowledge exists, but most skills are not possessed by the stakeholders. There is a need to bring professionals from other regions.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - While not directly stated, some stakeholders could take small parts of ownership. They are willing to participate in educational activities and promote circularity if given the tools.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Same capabilities as mentioned above need further development.

Scotland

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including
 - Presentations and group discussions according to format suggested by WP2 Lead
 - Briefing material with focus on challenges and opportunities
- **Attendees** included 15 representatives from
 - Enterprise Agencies (all Scottish regions represented)
 - Innovation Centres in Industrial Biotechnology and Built Environment
 - Scottish Government Circular Economy
 - Academia – Industrial Decarbonisation Research and Innovation Centre
 - Zero Waste Scotland – National Public Body for Circular Economy in Scotland
- **Reflections** centred around developing challenges and opportunities to inform ECIV going forward

Scotland

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Stakeholders recognized the challenges and opportunities, adding refreshed content and additional material. Challenges include scaling up equipment, regulatory standardization, and early-stage companies seeking 100% funding. Scotland has significant biomass feedstocks to support innovation. Process scale-up and regulatory sandbox opportunities were noted. Policy and public sector procurement are driving changes in other regions.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Stakeholders found the interregional collaboration interesting and saw potential in funding and contacts in Europe. There was a need for clearer understanding of the different levels of detail in each region's analysis.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - The process scale-up challenge was missing from the SWOT analysis. Investor confidence and integration of innovation into the market were also noted as missing. Challenges in dealing with businesses at different stages and the need for space to kit-out were highlighted.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - Additional areas of strength were identified, such as clean heat, construction materials, bio-based innovation, and offshore decommissioning.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - Areas of strength where Scotland could contribute include clean heat, construction materials, bio-based innovation, and offshore decommissioning. Potential opportunities include bio-based lubricants for the offshore oil industry and valorization of fish waste.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Scotland has strengths in industrial biotechnology, wet timber, fire safety, multi-story construction, and various emergent solutions. Place-based thinking to maximize local value chains and various feedstocks like marine biomass, agri-wastes, and whisky co-products.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - Same as above, with a focus on circular economy.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Numerous stakeholders are well connected to the Scottish Government, but there is a need for insight into successful practices elsewhere in Europe and understanding harmonization post-Brexit.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - Stakeholders are well connected at the national level but need to learn from international best practices and collaborate.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Strengthening skills provision, addressing regulatory issues, and improving scale-up infrastructure. Specific skills gaps include multi-skilled workers, construction sector skills, and bio-based skilled workers. Regulatory challenges include waste quality, waste classification, and lack of a framework for carbon accounting.

Northern Netherlands

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** with triple helix stakeholders where industry was represented by two ecosystem orchestrators, 12 participants in total

Northern Netherlands

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - There was a large consensus on the recognition of challenges and opportunities, with participants eager to detail themes and sectors into more specific topics.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Participants mentioned additional themes and believed there are more linkages to be found within the presented analysis and data.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Missing elements included the relation with geopolitics, opportunities from interregional EU collaboration, the role of government, the absence of water as a resource, the aspect of design, and consumer goods as a theme. Suggestions included moving from a basic SWOT analysis to a confrontation matrix and providing more insights on the economic structure of the regions, including lead firms and solution providers.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - No real surprises, but difficulties in interpreting the data were noted, which could lead to disregard of mentioned terms in "wrong" columns or different wording for the same topic.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - The similarities and relatedness of regions within the consortium were interesting. A mission-oriented methodology was preferred over a sectoral approach, aiming to engage stakeholders on the mission rather than primarily helping themselves.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Effectiveness on challenge roadmaps towards (sub)missions and monitoring of progress.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - From the perspective of value chains, optimizing these within the EU context or even within the RIV. Support and financial resources to reverse global value chains and economies of scale. AI skills or technology to advance digitalization in process industry and materials.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Partly available, or need to be developed.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - Participants have a relatively high sense of ownership. The Northern Netherlands is organized towards circular transition ambitions, and these stakeholders are part of that ecosystem.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Specific capabilities were not detailed, but the need for development was implied.

Normandy

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including
 - Brief presentation of the territorial analysis: Circular economy strategy, S3 strategy, sectors with highest turnover and intensive materials, main waste products, main material flows, SWOT
 - Presentation of the Normandy missions
 - Presentation of the interregional analysis: Common strategic sectors and common targets
 - Feedback on the presentation
 - Group discussion in five groups: Deploying the circular economy; The transition of the plastics industry; WEEE, batteries, metals; Construction; Circular bioeconomy
- **Attendees** included 55 representatives from research, companies, collectives, clusters, technical center and students
 - Research : bioplastic, building engineering, energy, materials, chemistry, physics, digital, management / business models
 - Companies : reuse of packaging, bioenergy, media, building (reuse), textiles, Reuse, cosmetic, pigments, CSR consultancy
 - Collectivities : Region, development agency
 - Cluster : agri-food, transport law, reuse, social enterprise, training, maritime, Ecodesign, industrial robotics, logistic, aquaculture, Incubator, sustainable territorial, development, agriculture
 - Technical center : plastic, microbiology,
 - Students in Circularity management

Normandy

- **Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis**

- Stakeholders recognized the identified challenges and opportunities. No particular comments on the analysis.

- **Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities**

- *Capabilities moving forward in the region:*
 - **Economic Models and Policies:** Develop viable economic models; Promote alternative economies (functionality, circularity, etc.); Harmonize European public policies; Engage in lobbying.
 - **Measurement and Prioritization:** Measure impacts using multiple indicators (CO2, resources, social, etc.); Prioritize impacts; Identify relevant and measurable indicators.
 - **Knowledge and Skills:** Improve observation to enhance knowledge and propose new recovery methods (connect sources and demand); Increase skills and workforce, especially in repair; Improve knowledge and monitor regulations, policies, and insurance systems; Learn from and replicate best practices in Normandy; Organize study trips; Enhance public communication and participatory science.
 - **Resource Sharing and Innovation:** Share resources (equipment, expertise, human resources, land, etc.) and knowledge; Develop micro-innovations, tailor-made innovations, tinkering, hybridization, low-tech solutions, etc.; Create a network of second-hand spare parts.
 - **Industry and Market Development:** Strengthen producer/consumer connections (e.g., plastics); Improve business waste collection and pooling; Prepare companies for new regulations; Develop recycling industries (construction, public works, textiles) and bio-sourced sectors.
 - **Collaboration and Stakeholder Involvement:** Form cross-sector working groups and involve stakeholders; Establish a joint, forward-looking, multidisciplinary observatory.
- *Stakeholder ownership:* Some stakeholders were very interested, and there have been many emails and calls since the workshop from stakeholders wanting to develop new projects

Wallonia

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including internal work based on consultation of stakeholders and partners to confirm and complete the results
- **Attendees** included stakeholders from the following sectors: Construction, Metallurgy, Water, Agri-Food, Plastics, Textiles, Biobased sector

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Yes, the challenges and opportunities were identified together with the stakeholders.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - No particular reactions were noted, as there was not enough information to imagine real opportunities.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Details about the capabilities of regions in terms of technological innovation were missing. However, stakeholders were willing to develop collaborations on the main interregional crossing sectors.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - No surprises were noted.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - No information.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

• Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:

- Standards and regulations: Need for regulations that encourage circular practices and solutions for restrictive regulations.
- Support and funding: Need for support in coaching, impact assessment, circular potential identification, and funding for innovative solutions or collaborative projects.
- Public procurement: Need for criteria that advantage circular products and services.
- Demonstration, innovation, and digital technology: Need for funding RDI collaborative projects to exploit regional expertise and boost innovation.
- Education and training: Need for increased knowledge on circular innovation practices.
- Information and awareness: Need for regular and accessible information about circular innovation opportunities.
- Collaboration at various levels: Need for national, European, and international collaboration.
- Regional resources: Need for workforce in specific sectors and development of expertise in circular innovation.

• Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:

- Industrialization of circular packaging: Process technologies, bio-based materials, SSDR system, design for circularity, smart production.
- Revalorization of by-products of the food industry: Standardization, new revalorization technologies, industrialization, new markets.
- Water regeneration in industrial processes: Pretreatment, regeneration processes, post-process treatments, nutrient recovery.
- Remanufacturing of components of renewable energy: Reverse logistics, remanufacturing process, operation and maintenance, recycled materials, design for remanufacturing.

• Available capabilities among the stakeholders:

- Most capabilities are developed in the region but need to be strengthened. Key economic players include industries in waste collection and treatment, construction, chemical industry, and manufacturing of metal products. Other sectors like agri-food, textiles, and water have also developed capabilities.

• Stakeholder ownership:

- A group of stakeholders in the innovation and circularity field is consolidated in the region. Some have specific roles and already ensure a leading role in developing innovative and circular solutions.

• Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:

- Construction sector: Tools and services for materials reuse, modularity in construction, focus on critical raw materials, RDI solutions, workforce training, new value chains.
- Metals and batteries sector: Identification and mapping of metals, RDI projects, circular design, regional expertise deployment.
- Water sector: Encouraging purified wastewater reuse, RDI solutions for resource extraction, water-efficient use in buildings.
- Agri-food and biomass sector: Identifying by-products, developing value chains, RDI projects for valorization.
- Cleantech: Deploying clean technologies for industry.
- Chemistry and polymers: Encouraging circular design in plastics, developing bioplastics value chains.

Navarra

Methodology

- **Stakeholder workshop** including the proposed method with an online interactive pool.
 - In the first part, the ECIV project, its objectives, and timeline were introduced
 - In the second part, focus was on regional circular economy context and existing projects in Navarra, along with common challenges
 - In the final part, an interactive poll with QR codes was used to identify main gaps in circular value chains. Participants voted on challenges and opportunities, which were then digitalized and linked to capabilities.
- **Attendees** included 50 participants with intermediate stakeholders: Clusters, universities, research centers, territorial actors, business organizations

Reflection 1: (Inter)regional analysis

- *Recognition of identified challenges and opportunities:*
 - Legal challenges: Regulation that restricts circularity with legal barriers. Excessive bureaucracy. Difficulty in understanding and staying updated on new regulations.
 - Market challenges: Supply chain problems with secondary materials in terms of quantity and quality. Increased product costs, with linear economy still being cheaper. End consumer lack of knowledge about the complexity of value chains. Lack of market demand for public, private, and industrial purchases.
 - Technological challenges: Difficulty in making changes to product design and production lines. Need for treatment technologies for preparing products, components, and materials. Problems in identifying appropriate technology or dealing with immature/non-industrialized technology.
 - Knowledge challenges: Lack of specialized technical knowledge. Lack of qualified personnel. Need for new training skills. Importance of sharing good practices and success-failure cases. General lack of knowledge and social awareness.
 - Funding challenges: Need for financial support for new circular business models or services. Complexity in aid management. Short deadlines for advancing real projects. Lack of economic incentives for joint systemic change. Need for new specialized financing lines.
 - Collaboration challenges: Beginnings of culture change towards intersectoral collaboration. Need to facilitate interconnection between companies and learn more about territorial capabilities. Stakeholders need to identify themselves within a value chain change. Lack of solutions for reverse logistics to create synergies.
- *Reactions and thoughts related to the interregional analysis:*
 - Stakeholders showed interest in the fact that other regions share similar potential circular challenges.
- *Missing aspects in the analysis:*
 - Not at the moment, as it was the first event related to ECIV directly involving stakeholders.
- *Surprising aspects in the analysis:*
 - Not at the moment.
- *Most interesting aspects in the analysis:*
 - Potential collaborative projects in circular economy among regions in Europe.

• Reflection 2: Stakeholder capabilities

- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the region:*
 - Legal challenges, Market challenges, Technological challenges, Knowledge challenges, Funding challenges, Collaboration challenges.
- *Capabilities needed moving forward in the development of circular economy in the region:*
 - Industrialization of circular packaging: Process technologies for large-scale industrialization with new materials. Packaging made from bio-based materials. SSDR system for returnable packaging. Design for circularity. Smart and digital production of recycled and recyclable packaging.
 - Revalorization of by-products of the food industry: Homogenization and standardization of usable material. Development of new revalorization technologies for animal/human food. Development of new revalorization technologies for other uses (materials, packaging, fertilizers). Industrialization of processing new products. Creation of new markets.
 - Water regeneration in industrial processes: Pretreatment before processing. Regeneration processes in industry. Post-process treatments for reuse. Recovery of nutrients from wastewater.
 - Remanufacturing of components of renewable energy: Reverse logistics of components. Remanufacturing process and certifications. Operation and maintenance of components. Recycled and recyclable raw materials. Design of components for remanufacturing.
- *Available capabilities among the stakeholders:*
 - Not detailed.
- *Stakeholder ownership:*
 - Yes, the territorial challenges will be conducted with the ownership of clusters or industrial organizations.
- *Capabilities that need to be developed further in the region:*
 - Continuing focusing on collaborative projects.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Project No. 101161155. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix 2

GAP analysis and analysis of circular economy country profiles – ECIV

Dalarna/NMS in collaboration with WSP

2025-03-03

Contents

The purpose of this report is to show, and discuss, results from a compilation of existing GAP analyses in the nine ECIV regions, and on a European level.

- **Focus:** Identifying existing GAP analyses on a regional (& National) and European (& EU) level, and describing key insights. On the European level, GAP analyses for a number of strategic value chains are also included.

p. 3 – Point of Departure, Method & Sources

p. 7 – Summary of Key Observations

p. 14 – European (& EU) level

p.23 – Strategic European Value Chains

p. 26 – Regional (& National) level

Point of Departure, Method & Sources

The following slides describe the point of departure, and method and sources, for the compilation of existing GAP analyses.

Point of departure

A **GAP analysis** is a strategic tool used to compare a current state with a potential or desired state. It helps identify the differences (or “gaps”) between the two states, allowing to develop strategies to bridge them.

In our literature search, we have not been able to find existing GAP reports on circular economy for all nine regions. We have therefore also included other reports with similar content (elaborated on the next slide).

Method & Sources

Two main sources have been used for the compilation of GAP analyses on the regional (& National) level:

Circularity Gap Reports (CGR) and **Circular Economy Profiles (EEA)**.

On a European (& EU) level, **reports and statistics from EEA** have mainly been used. For value chains on a European (& Global) level, sources include reports from the European Commission, the EU project RegioGreenTex and the One Planet network.

CGR: Circularity Gap Reports

- provides a comprehensive GAP analysis, describing gaps between current and desired circularity with actions and policy recommendations
- published by the organization Circle Economy, which has been working since 2011 to promote a circular economy through research and collaboration

EEA: Circular Economy Country Profile

- not GAP reports, but provide an overview of current state and the way forward, including national policies, best practices and data and statistics
- compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Topic Centre on Circular Economy and Resource Use (ETC/CE)

Full GAP-reports

Country profiles

	North Middle Sweden	Helsinki-Uusimaa	Wallonia	Gabrovo	Normandy	Navarra	Scotland	Lithuania	Northern Netherlands	European level
CGR	X						X		X	<i>(global)</i>
EEA	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X*

* Not Circular Economy Profile on the EU level – but other EEA reports and statistics. Other sources have also been used on the European level, focusing on key value chains.

Summary of Key Observations

The following slides summarize key observations from the GAP analyses, divided by:

- European (& EU) level
- Regional (& National) level

The key observations focus on current states, and strategies to reach desired states (broadly viewed as increased circularity).

Key sectors and themes in focus are also highlighted, on an overarching level.

European (& EU) level

Current State

- **Circularity Rate:** The EU is 11,8% circular (2023). Europe consumes a higher proportion of recycled materials than other world regions, but improvement has been slow in recent years. Meanwhile, material demand is projected to increase over the coming years.
- **Material Consumption:** For the EU economy to function in its current manner, more than 8 billion tonnes of material are used every year. 5 billion tonnes are used to cover needs/desires of EU citizens.
- **Resource Extraction:** 68% of 8 billion tonnes originates from natural resources extracted within the EU, including non-metallic minerals, biomass, fossil energy materials/carriers, and metal ores.
- **Policy Leadership:** The circular economy concept has gained political momentum in Europe. A comprehensive set of new circularity policies has been introduced at EU level, and national actions have intensified. Many nations are however at the early stages of implementation.

Figure 2. Circular material use rate by EU country

Figure 2.1 Global material use by resource type

Source: IRP, 2019.

European (& EU) level

Strategies to Reach Desired State

- **The Circular Vision for Europe:** Outlines what circularity should look like, structured around a life-cycle approach that covers the whole value chain in the EU economy.
- **Actions for Increased Circularity:**
 - Prioritise circularity approaches to reduce raw material demand, activate eco-design requirements, and promote product service system models.
 - Extend product lifetimes, including cost management and increased trust in repairs and upgrades.
 - Shift the waste sector to provide high-quality recycled materials for the industry.
- **Other Considerations:**
 - The affluence of EU citizens are undoubtedly a factor in high consumption rates and behavioural changes are needed.
 - Targets are important for driving and measuring change, however, there are indications of low or moderate likelihood of current ambitions being achieved in the coming years.
 - A successful circular transition requires full societal engagement, however, there is currently limited analysis of social equity, inclusion and accessibility issues.

Figure 1.1 The touchpoints for achieving a circular economy in Europe, with key factors associated with each touchpoint

Source: EEA.

Figure 4.1 Actions for increased circularity

BEFORE USE		DURING USE		AFTER USE	
	REFUSE		RETAIN		RECYCLE
	RETHINK		REUSE AND SHARE		RETURN
	REDUCE		REPAIR		REMANUFACTURE

Source: Developed by EEA based on Potting et al., 2017.

European (& EU) level

GAP Analyses for Value Chains

- **Lithium-ion battery:**

- **Current state:** Challenges in recycling processes and material recovery, particularly for critical materials like lithium, cobalt, and nickel. There are also financial constraints, inadequate regulatory frameworks, and a lack of awareness and engagement among stakeholders.
- **Strategies to reach desired state:** Invest in R&D to enhance recycling technologies, implement better material recovery systems, provide financial incentives, create coherent regulations across regions, and conduct awareness campaigns to promote CE practices.

- **Textile:**

- **Current state:** The industry faces a lack of technologies to efficiently recycle textiles and reduce waste, leading to a high percentage of textile waste ending up in landfills. There are also financial constraints, inadequate regulations, and low consumer demand for recycled textiles.
- **Strategies to reach desired state:** Optimize production and recycling processes, improve material recovery systems, provide financial support for R&D, harmonize regulations, and promote awareness and adoption of circular practices.

- **Construction**

- **Current state:** Circular economy principles are not well integrated into the planning and design stages of construction projects. There is also insufficient use of public procurement to drive circularity, limited financial instruments, inadequate policies, and a lack of awareness among stakeholders.
- **Strategies to reach desired state:** Incorporate circular economy principles in planning and design, leverage public procurement, develop financial instruments, strengthen policies and regulations, and conduct awareness campaigns to educate stakeholders on circular practices.

Regional (& National) level

Strategies to Reach Desired State

- **Scenarios (North Middle Sweden, Northern Netherlands, Scotland):**
 - Common focus areas include the built environment, agriculture, manufacturing, and reducing fossil fuel use. Specific regional focuses include mobility (Sweden and Scotland), behavioral change (Scotland), and repair and high-value recycling (Netherlands).
- **Future Policy Plans (all but Scotland):**
 - The most prevalent theme is economic investments for circularity, e.g. targeting digitization, modernization of infrastructure, and waste management.
- **The Way Forward (all):**
 - The regions are different in character: A few are frontrunners when it comes to circularity, whereas others are more linear
 - Regardless, all regions face similar challenges and needs that require fundamental shifts, including behavioural shifts, harmonization of regulation, strategic planning, development of infrastructure, R&D, economic incentives, jobs and skills

Key Sectors, Themes and Considerations

Sectors

- Throughout the GAP analyses, both national and European, three sectors are mentioned most frequent, including: Construction, Food and Agriculture, and Manufacturing

Themes

- Recurrent themes within the GAP analyses include Jobs and Skills, Waste Management, Funding, Regulation, Awareness, and R&D

Considerations

- Within the majority of regions, there is a stronger basis regarding *current states* than *desired states* and *strategies* to bridge the gaps
- Regarding current states, statistics with certain key indicators are highlighted and followed up over time by e.g. EEA. However, it is important to note these do not convey the full picture of the country's state regarding circular economy.

European (& EU) level

The following slides develop insights on the European (& EU) level from studied reports, divided by:

- Europe (general)
- Value Chains (sectoral)

Sources are included on each slide for further reading and more detailed information.

Europe

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Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Europe is 11,5% circular (2022) and consumes a higher proportion of recycled materials than other world regions. Yet, improvement has been slow in recent years, and along with projected increased material demand by 2030, the EU is currently not on track to double circular material use by 2030.
- **Material Consumption:** For the EU economy to function in its current manner, more than 8 billion tonnes of material are used every year. 5 billion tonnes are used to cover needs/desires of EU citizens annually (3 billions are 'locked up' resources in their present function and are not available to be returned to the production cycle).
- **Resource Extraction:** 68% of 8 billion tonnes originates from natural resources extracted within the EU, including non-metallic minerals, biomass, fossil energy materials/carriers, and metal ores.

Figure 2. Circular material use rate by EU country

Europe

The Touchpoints for Achieving a Circular Economy in Europe

- **The circular vision for Europe** outlines what circularity should look like, structured around a life-cycle approach that covers the whole value chain in the EU economy:
 - Safe and sustainable design
 - Efficient production
 - Sustainable consumption
 - Longer and better use of products
 - Waste as a resource
- Substantial movement towards greater circularity will entail significant changes across all aspects of material use, including the practices that underlie how products are created and consumed.
- Implementing the principles of a circular economy will lead to the establishment of new norms and profound changes to Europe's production and consumption patterns, playing a significant role in lessening their environmental impacts.

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Europe

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Resources and Waste – Key messages

- Resource extraction and processing cause severe impacts on ecosystems, contribute to climate change and increase pollution levels
- Decreasing resource extraction and increasing the use of secondary raw materials would deliver greater strategic autonomy for the EU and reduce environmental impacts
- Focusing recycling operations on the production of high quality secondary raw materials is critical to enabling a closed loop from waste generation back to industrial inputs

Europe

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Policy leadership – Key messages

- A comprehensive set of new circularity policies has been introduced at EU level
- National actions have intensified but many are still at the early stages of implementation
- Monitoring the circular transition is critical and continued development of reporting systems is required at EU, national and sectoral level

Figure 3.2 EU Member States with adopted national circular economy strategies (2022)

Source: EC, 2019.

Europe

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Implementing Circular Actions – Key messages

- Circularity approaches that reduce raw material demand should be prioritised, including the activation of eco-design requirements and promotion of product service system models
- Extending the lifetime of consumer products is important in a circular economy and this will require attention to managing costs and increasing trust in repaired and upgraded items
- The waste sector must transition towards a business model focused on providing high quality recycled materials as feedstock for industry

Figure 4.1 Actions for increased circularity

BEFORE USE	DURING USE	AFTER USE
RECYCLE		
RETURN		
REPAIR		
	REMANUFACTURE	

Source: Developed by EEA based on Potting et al., 2017.

Europe

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Consumption in a Circular Economy – Key messages

- EU material consumption shows a modest relative decoupling from economic growth but consumption levels per capita remain too high
- The aspirations and affluence of EU citizens are undoubtedly a factor in high consumption rates and more effort is needed to change their behaviour
- Business operators are introducing more circular product offerings, but the pace is slow and stronger policy action may be needed to speed up this change

Europe

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Just Transition to a Circular Economy – Key messages

- Circular economy systems are not inherently socially beneficial just because they are circular
- A successful circular transition requires full societal engagement but there is currently limited analysis of social equity, inclusion and accessibility issues
- The impact of transitioning to a circular economy on communities and livelihoods in the global south must be considered to avoid exacerbating existing inequalities

Outlook and Future Considerations – Key messages

- The circular economy concept has gained political momentum but further measures are needed to realise changes in consumption and production patterns
- Targets are important for driving and measuring change, however, assessment of current circular ambitions indicates a low or moderate likelihood of them being achieved in the coming years
- Near-term actions to accelerate the circular transition include setting clear targets, supporting emerging secondary raw material markets and further developing circularity monitoring
- The circular transition will require moderation of current consumption patterns, effective extension of product lifespans and widespread use of recycled materials as sustainable feedstocks for industry

Europe

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Just Transition to a Circular Economy – Key messages

- Circular economy systems are not inherently socially beneficial just because they are circular
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- The circular transition will require moderation of current consumption patterns, effective extension of product lifespans and widespread use of recycled materials as sustainable feedstocks for industry

Value Chains / Lithium-ion battery

Current State / Gaps:

- **Technical:** Challenges in recycling processes and material recovery. Specifically, the report mentions the need for improved technologies to efficiently recycle lithium, cobalt, nickel, and other critical materials used in Li-ion batteries.
- **Material:** Inefficiencies in material usage and recovery. The report highlights the loss of valuable materials during the recycling process and the need for better material recovery systems.
- **Economic:** Financial constraints and lack of investment. The report identifies insufficient funding for research and development, high costs of recycling technologies, and the need for financial incentives to promote circular practices.
- **Regulatory:** Inadequate regulatory frameworks. The report points out the lack of coherent regulations across different regions, which hinders the development of a unified circular economy strategy for Li-ion batteries.
- **Behavioral:** Lack of awareness and engagement. The report emphasizes the need for increased awareness among stakeholders, including manufacturers, consumers, and policymakers, about the benefits of circular economy practices.

Strategies / Actions Proposed:

- **Improve recycling processes and technologies:** Invest in R&D to enhance recycling technologies for lithium, cobalt, nickel, and other critical materials. Develop more efficient and cost-effective methods for material recovery.
- **Enhance material recovery and usage efficiency:** Implement better material recovery systems to minimize loss of valuable materials in the recycling process. Optimize design of batteries for easier disassembly and recycling.
- **Increase investment and financial support:** Provide financial incentives and funding for R&D in recycling technologies. This includes grants, subsidies, and tax incentives to encourage investment in CE practices.
- **Develop and implement better regulatory frameworks:** Create coherent regulations across regions to support a unified CE strategy for Li-ion batteries. Harmonize standards and policies to facilitate cross-border cooperation.
- **Raise awareness and promote engagement in circular practices:** Conduct awareness campaigns and educational programs to inform stakeholders (manufacturers, consumers, policymakers) about the benefits of CE practices.

Value Chains / Textile

Current State / Gaps:

- **Technical:** Lack of technologies to efficiently recycle textiles and reduce waste during production. Bottlenecks include lack of sorting technologies to separate different types of fibers and difficulty in removing contaminants from recycled textiles.
- **Material:** Loss of valuable materials during the production and recycling processes and lack of material recovery systems. Bottlenecks include high percentage of textile waste ending up in landfills and limited availability of high-quality recycled fibers.
- **Economic:** Insufficient funding for R&D, high costs of recycling technologies, and lack of financial incentives to promote circular practice, especially support for SMEs.
- **Regulatory:** Lack of coherent regulations across regions, hindering development of a unified CE strategy for textiles. Bottlenecks include absence of standardized guidelines for textile recycling and lack of enforcement of existing regulations.
- **Behavioral:** Lack of awareness among stakeholders about benefits of CE practices. Bottlenecks include low consumer demand for recycled textiles and resistance among traditional manufacturers.

Strategies / Actions Proposed:

- **Optimize production and recycling processes:** Invest in R&D to enhance recycling technologies. Develop more advanced, efficient and cost-effective methods for material recovery.
- **Improve material efficiency and reduce waste:** Implement better material recovery systems to minimize loss of valuable materials during production and recycling processes. Optimize the design of textiles for easier disassembly and recycling, and promote eco-design principles and take-back schemes.
- **Increase funding and financial support:** Provide financial incentives and funding for R&D in recycling technologies. This includes grants, subsidies, and tax incentives to encourage investment in circular economy practices, especially for SMEs.
- **Harmonize and strengthen regulatory frameworks:** Create coherent regulations across regions to support the development of a unified CE strategy for textiles. Harmonize standards and policies and enforce existing regulations.
- **Promote awareness and adoption of circular practices:** Conduct awareness campaigns and educational programs to inform stakeholders about the benefits of CE practices.

Value Chains / Construction

Current State / Gaps:

- **Planning and design:** Lack of integration of circular principles. The report mentions the need for incorporating circular economy principles in the planning and design stages of construction projects.
- **Public procurement:** Insufficient use of procurement to drive circularity. The report highlights the potential of public procurement to promote circular practices in the construction sector.
- **Financial:** Limited financial instruments to support circular practices. The report identifies the need for financial instruments, such as grants and subsidies, to support the adoption of circular practices in the construction industry.
- **Regulatory:** Inadequate policies and regulations. The report points out the lack of coherent policies and regulations to support the circular economy in the construction sector.
- **Awareness:** Lack of knowledge and understanding of circular practices. The report emphasizes the need for increased awareness among stakeholders, including architects, builders, and policymakers, about the benefits of circular economy practices.

Strategies / Actions Proposed:

- **Integrate circular principles in planning and design:** Incorporate circular economy principles in the planning and design stages of construction projects. This includes designing buildings for disassembly and reuse.
- **Leverage public procurement to promote circularity:** Use public procurement as a tool to drive the adoption of circular practices in the construction sector.
- **Develop and implement financial instruments to support circular practices:** Provide financial support, such as grants and subsidies, to encourage the adoption of circular practices in the construction industry.
- **Strengthen policies and regulations to support circular economy:** Create coherent policies and regulations to promote CE in the construction sector. This involves harmonizing standards and policies across regions.
- **Raise awareness and educate stakeholders on circular practices:** Conduct awareness campaigns and educational programs to inform stakeholders about the benefits of circular economy practices. E.g. architects, builders, policymakers.

Regional (& National level)

The following slides develop insights on the Regional (& National) level from studied reports, divided by each region/nation.

Sources are included on each slide for further reading and more detailed information.

North Middle Sweden / Sweden

Sizing the gap

- **Circularity Rate:** Sweden is 3.4% circular according to CGR, 9% to EEA
- **Material consumption:** 257.5 million tonnes of materials annually (CGR)
- **Resource Extraction:** 265.3 million tonnes of minerals, metals, and biomass annually; nearly half is used domestically, the rest is exported (CGR)
- **Sectors:** The construction sector accounts for 48% of material consumption; the biggest category in terms of resource use (CGR). Structure of the economy: Agriculture: 1.1 % Industry: 26.0 % Services: 72.9 % (EEA).
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 85,100 people employed in CE sectors (13.8 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.7 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021). (EEA)
- **Exports:** 89.6 million tonnes of final products with an associated footprint of 137.9 million tonnes.
- **Imports:** 90.3 million tonnes of goods, with a total import footprint of 130.1 million tonnes.

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Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010, 2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

North Middle Sweden / Sweden

Bridging the gap

Construct a circular built environment

- Reduce new materials inputs and promote the reuse of construction and demolition waste
- Reduce material losses and emissions in construction by using durable, lightweight materials, prioritize local sources, and increase the use of secondary materials
- Reduce energy use in buildings through energy-efficient appliances, smart meters, and lower room temperatures, while shifting from waste-to-energy to geothermal heat pumps

Cultivate a thriving food system

- Reduce food consumption to and minimize food waste through better practices and anaerobic digestion
- Shift to vegetarian diets reducing the consumption of resource and emissions-intensive foods like meat and processed items
- Promote sustainable food production and consumption by prioritizing local and seasonal foods, scaling organic farming, and reducing the use of artificial fertilizers

Make manufacturing circular

- Enhance manufacturing efficiency by reducing material losses and scrap, utilize technological advances, and promote closed-loop recycling
- Create durable machinery and equipment to extend their lifetimes, boost repair and rental services, and reduce the need for new material inputs

Reshape extractive industries:

- Restrict resource extraction by limiting logging, mining, and fishing in overexploited areas

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Drive clean mobility forward:

- Promote carsharing, carpooling, trip-chaining, and park-and-ride systems
- Support flexible work-from-home environments to reduce daily commutes
- Make vehicles more efficient and durable by incentivizing fuel-efficient and lightweight designs, extending vehicle lifetimes through circular business models and preventive maintenance

Design conscious consumables:

- Reduce plastic and chemical production by shifting away from single-use plastics, increasing reuse and recycling, and prioritizing bio-based chemicals
- Transform the textiles industry by using vegan, natural fibers, increasing recycled content, and promoting durable garment design and clothing sharing
- Encourage the purchase of local and durable furniture, promoting repair, reuse, and refurbishing to reduce waste and emissions
- Minimize appliance use, promote durable and lightweight designs, and encourage take-back programs for repair and reuse

North Middle Sweden / Sweden

Root Causes and Actions Needed

- **Legal and Regulatory** – Current policies target product use phase, not production, and there is a need for holistic circularity approach. Some actions include EPR, eco-design, reduction targets based on material use, quotas for secondary materials in products, tax shifts.
- **Economic and Financial** – Economic growth relies on consumption, leading to resource extraction and waste, and market for recycled materials struggles against virgin materials. Some actions include circular public procurement, research on policy for circular capacity in SMEs, monitoring and addressing rebound effects.
- **Technological and Capacity-Based** – Technical barriers in sorting and recycling waste streams, and lack of capacity to assess quality of secondary materials. Some actions include material specifications and design guidelines, improved recycling, supporting businesses in circular efforts, especially SMEs.
- **Cultural and Behavioural** – High consumption rates lead to significant waste, and traditional ownership mindsets result in inefficient material use. Some actions include fostering shift towards sharing/second-hand shopping/reduced ownership, encouraging eco-design principles and circular practices, and promoting collaboration across industries.

3/5

The Way Forward

- Sweden is **more linear than it appears** on paper, with high levels of extraction and consumption, and prosperous living conditions for its residents –as such, it has a particularly **strong responsibility to drive circularity** and cut its per capita ecological footprint
- The report conveys how the **circularity can be substantially increased** from 3.4% to 7.6% – in doing so, the country can cut its material footprint by 42.6%
- With a wide and diverse pool of **local resources**, Sweden could shift its consumption to domestically sourced—and sustainably produced—products, rather than relying on imports with hard-to-control circularity, sustainability and ethics
- As a key **global provider of raw materials**, Sweden's role represents an opportunity for impact beyond its borders
- Sweden is **well-positioned** to take on the challenge of going circular: it boasts a low-carbon economy, strong climate ambitions, and technical and behavioural capacity

Northern Netherlands / Netherlands

Sizing the gap

- **Circularity Rate:** The Netherlands is 24.5% circular (CGR), 31% (EEA)
- **Material Consumption:** 221 million tonnes of materials annually (CGR)
- **Resource Extraction:** 116 million tonnes of minerals, metals, and biomass annually (CGR)
- **Sectors:** Mobility and Nutrition are the biggest contributors to the Netherlands' societal need footprint, taking up almost half of the entire consumption footprint (CGR). Structure of the economy: Agriculture: 1.9 % Industry: 20.8 % Services: 77.3 % (EEA)
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 105,173 people employed in CE sectors (2.5 % of EU total in 2021) People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.1 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021). (EEA)
- **Exports:** 210 million tonnes of final products with an associated footprint of 487 million tonnes and 14 million tonnes of waste (CGR)
- **Imports:** 145 million tonnes of direct products and their associated footprint, 403 million tonnes (CGR)

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Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010, 2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Northern Netherlands / Netherlands

2/4

Bridging the gap

• **Advanced construction practices**

- Maintain and repurpose existing buildings instead of demolishing them
- Enhance the cycling of construction materials and demolition waste, which eliminates the need for virgin material extraction

• **Circular agriculture and food system**

- Stop the import and export of animal products and feed, localize animal cultivation, and use local agricultural waste for livestock feed
- Eliminate food waste from production to consumption and optimize the use of biowaste, reducing food waste to zero per person and increasing the recycling of biowaste

• **Shifting from fossil fuels to renewable sources**

- Transition to renewable energy sources like solar and wind, decarbonize the energy grid, and adjust industrial activities to be compatible with renewable energy
- Halt all raw material imports and exports of fossil fuels, leading to a de-fossilized domestic energy system and trade profile

• **Repair, manufacturing and high value recycling**

- Double the material use of the repair sector to extend the life of manufactured goods, reduce imports, and decrease domestic production of new products
- Doubling the volume of high-value recycling and the share of recycled materials in imports, reducing the need for virgin material inputs

Northern Netherlands / Netherlands

3/4

Jobs and skills – driving the transition:

- **Construction:** Design for disassembly, on-site recycling, stimulation of secondary materials in procurement, evaluators of secondary materials, greater knowledge within the managing of building information.
- **Agrifood:** Extended skills in soil health, also greater CE knowledge in companies producing livestock feed made from waste flow.
- **Manufacturing:** Design for disassembly and reuse, greater understanding of circular products, repair and refurbishment skills, and a greater understanding of the demand/supply for/of refurbished products,

The Way Forward

- The report conveys how the circularity of the country can be substantially increased from 24.5% to 70%.
- The explored scenarios will entail fundamental shifts to the way the Dutch economy operates, spanning from how infrastructure is built and maintained, how food is produced and how we design, manufacture and repair goods, to how we shape our future energy systems.
- The Netherlands is a frontrunner in the race to circularity and has a real opportunity to contribute to a rich global knowledge bank on the circular economy.

Scotland

1/4

Sizing the gap

- **Circularity Rate:** Scotland is 1.3% circular
- **Material Consumption:** 119.4 million tonnes of materials annually.
- **Resource Extraction:** 125.4 million tonnes of minerals, metals, and biomass annually; mainly extraction of fossil fuels.
- **Sectors:** the Agrifood, Manufacturing and Services industries concentrate the largest shares of the country's material flows.
- **Exports:** 100.2 million tonnes of final products with an associated footprint of 120.7 million tonnes.
- **Imports:** 74.7 million tonnes of RMEs with an associated footprint of 113.2 million tonnes.

Scotland

Bridging the gap

• Build a circular built environment

- Optimize the building stock expansion by reducing new construction, increasing the reuse of building materials, and enhancing renovation efforts
- Increase building occupancy by regulating second homes and Airbnbs, and promoting co-housing and multifunctional spaces
- Scale resource-efficient construction practices and implement deep renovation to reduce construction waste and energy demand

• Nurture a circular food system

- Promote a balanced diet with a caloric intake of 2,700 per day, favoring plant-based foods, and reducing avoidable food waste
- Shift to organic, local, and seasonal food production to reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers, lower transport distances, and decrease dependence on greenhouse-grown foods

• Champion circular manufacturing

- Improve resource efficiency in manufacturing by reducing metal inputs, cutting yield losses, and reusing scrap materials
- Extend the lifetimes of machinery, equipment, and vehicles through remanufacturing, refurbishment, and other R-strategies, reducing material and carbon footprints while boosting circularity and job creation

2/4

• Rethink mobility

- Promote a car-free lifestyle, improved public transport, and flexible work arrangements to reduce private car use and fuel consumption
- Drive efficient, lightweight, and electric vehicles to reduce material and fuel use

• Welcome a circular lifestyle

- Promote a low-impact lifestyle focused on minimalism and conscious living, aiming to reduce consumption, extend product lifetimes, and encourage recycling and eco-friendly alternatives to lower environmental pressures and resource intensity

• Tackle Scotland's import footprint

- Shift away from high-impact material imports and focus on domestic production

• Advance circular decommissioning

- Focus on reusing valuable materials from decommissioned energy infrastructure to reduce the need for virgin materials, cut energy use, and create new value chains and job opportunities

Scotland

3/4

Transforming the Scottish economy – with and for people

- **Labor market:** Transitioning to CE could create approximately 59 000 new jobs, many of which is in the research and development sector
- **Resilience:** A CE is more self reliant, which build greater resilience against forecasted resource constraints and price volatility
- **Equality:** A less import-dependent economy also internalizes the externalities of production which can have positive impacts on countries in the Global South
- **Health:** CE prevents landfilling and incineration of waste, use of hazardous materials, and GHG emissions which reduce pollution.
- **Cultural:** CE is connected to the 'sharing economy' which can contribute to an increased sense of community

The Way Forward

- The report conveys how the circularity of the country can be substantially increased from 1.3% to 11.8%
- The explored scenarios will entail fundamental shifts to the way the Scottish economy operates, spanning from how buildings are built and maintained, how food is produced and how we design – the scenarios results in environmental as well as socioeconomic benefits
- While Scotland exhibits unsustainable levels of consumption and extraction, there's a general acceptance towards using CE as a mean for achieving the country's decarbonization goals which is an important step in leaving the linear economy behind

Gabrovo / Bulgaria

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Bulgaria is 5 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 162.4 million tonnes DMC (2.6 % of EU27 total in 2022) 24.4 tonnes DMC/person (171.8 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 3.5 % Industry: 28.9 % Services: 67.6 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 52,323 people employed in CE sectors (1.2 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.5 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010,2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Gabrovo / Bulgaria

2/4

Existing Policy Framework:

- **Strategy and Action Plan for the transition to a circular economy** for the period 2022–2027
 - The strategy formulates **three strategic goals**: 1: Green and competitive economy; 2. Less waste and more resources; 3. Economy that benefits consumers
- Circular economy in other policies include **National Development Programme Bulgaria 2030**
 - **Circular policy elements** focus on sustainable raw material use, stimulating and increasing recyclable materials, enhancing circular economy knowledge, boosting recycled and recovered waste, reducing waste impact, preventing waste generation, promoting reuse, and innovating for a circular economy transition in enterprises

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Regulatory and Financial Framework for Waste Management**, introduced by the Waste Management Act.
 - **Financial support programmes** targeting Circular Economy, e.g. Programme "Environment" 2021–2027; "Innovations and Competitiveness" (OPIK, financing measures for SMEs)
 - **Technology & innovation**, e.g. Programme "Competitiveness and Innovation in Enterprises" 2021–2027
 - **Green/Circular/Sustainable public procurement**, e.g. Mandatory Green Public Procurement in Bulgaria
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - **Bulgarian Association Circular Textile (BACT)** unites companies, experts in separate collection and utilization of textile waste as well as experts in preparation for reuse and its entry in the second-hand clothing market
 - **S.W.A.N project** funded by INTERREG Balkan–Mediterranean 2014–2020, study of the generated waste in the country, the possible business models for treatment and study of opportunities in other countries

Gabrovo / Bulgaria

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- **Bulgarian SMEs** face significant challenges in waste management and the adoption of circular economy models due to lack of awareness – to address these issues, there's need for better information, guidance, and public support.
- Bulgaria recommends a **harmonized EU approach** to integrate circular business models and resource efficiency criteria into product policies. This includes promoting eco-design, improving the quality and traceability of recycled materials, and leveraging digitalization to support circular economy initiatives.
- On a **national level**, commitment for better coordination, improved strategic planning and effective institutional cooperation within CE is advocated.

Future policy plans

- **Economic Transformation Programme**
 - targeted support incl. grants and financial instruments to Bulgarian enterprises to facilitate their transition to a digital, low-carbon and resource-efficient economy
 - Fund 1 "Growth and Innovation", Fund 2 "Green Transition and the Circular Economy", and Fund 3 "Investing in Climate Neutrality and Digital Transformation"
- **Fund for promoting the technological and green transition of the agriculture**
 - targeted support incl. grants and financial instruments to Bulgarian farmers, focusing on green and digital investments
 - The direction "Investments in technological and environmental modernization" of the Fund, with a budget EUR 325.2 million, supports investments in circular economy models

Normandy / France

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** France is 17 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 759.9 million tonnes DMC (11.9 % of EU27 total in 2022) 11.2 tonnes DMC/person (78.5 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 1.9 % Industry: 20.6 % Services: 77.5 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 523,904 people employed in CE sectors (12.2 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.8 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010, 2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Normandy / France

2/4

Existing Policy Framework:

- Following **the Circular Economy Roadmap** (2018), **the Anti Waste Law** (2020) and the **Climate and Resilience law** (2021), several measures are being developed to speed up the CE transition, e.g:
 - New EPR schemes provided for in the anti-waste law, National observatory for reuse as an extension of the Climate and Resilience Act, New consumer information measures, including reparability scores, durability scores, and requirements to combat greenwashing
- In 2022 France introduced an **ecological planning process**
- In 2022 France introduced a **3R strategy on plastic packaging**
- Many French **towns and cities launched zero waste initiatives** following the call for projects launched by ADEME in 2014
- Circular economy policy elements in **other policies** include e.g. Public Procurement, Waste Prevention Plan 2021–2027, PEMW diagnosis in the building sector, the national low carbon strategy

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Product-related policies**, e.g. Reparability and durability score, and The repair bonus.
 - **Producer / supplier responsibility**, e.g. The EPR scheme for construction products and materials for the building sector, and PMCB EPR scheme
 - **Financial support programmes**, e.g. France 2030 for the development of recycling
 - **Green/Circular/Sustainable public procurement**, e.g. study on the effect of mandatory targets for public buyers
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - The State has pushed **companies to develop a roadmap** to accelerate the transition to the circular economy of the **construction** ecosystem
 - As part of the 3R strategy on **plastics**, many federations have drawn up **3Rs sector roadmaps**

Normandy / France

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- The **costs associated with changing the model**: investment costs, but also organisational costs, particularly for the development of short circular economy loops, which often require the involvement of other players in the value chain or the development of collective approaches, which is far from companies' usual practices.
- The **globalisation of value chains**, which makes a value chain approach more difficult.

Future policy plans

- **Two measures** relating to the circular economy have been included in **the recovery plan**
 - one relating to the modernisation of sorting centres to develop recycling, and the development of sorting at source and the recovery of bio-waste
 - the other one focused on reduction and recycling especially on plastic waste

Lithuania

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Lithuania is 4 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 56.9 million tonnes DMC (0.9 % of EU27 total in 2022) 20.1 tonnes DMC/person (141.3 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 3.3 % Industry: 26.7 % Services: 70.0 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 39,115 people employed in CE sectors (0.9 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 2.8 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010,2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Lithuania

2/4

Existing Policy Framework:

- **Guidelines for the Lithuanian transition to a circular economy by 2035** was approved by the Government in July 2023. The guideline outline priority directions where intervention is vital:
 - Industry, Construction, Bioeconomy, Transport, Waste, Consumption
- Circular economy issues are also addressed in the following policies:
 - **The National waste prevention and management plan**, which supports reuse and repair centers and addresses food loss.
 - **The Agriculture and rural development strategic plan**, which concerns agriculture and bioeconomy, developing of organic farming, and the shortening of supply chains

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Circular business models** program by Ministry of Social Security and Labor
 - **Financial measures** from Ministry of Environment and Ministry of the Economy and Innovation
 - **Green public procurement** mandatory since 2023
 - **Food waste** management rules by Ministry of Environment
 - **Construction waste** criteria by Ministry of the Environment
 - **Waste management** requirements by Ministry of Environment
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - A **startup** company established by **organic waste** experts returning food waste back to food chain
 - **Circular transport** through electricity bus **Dancer**, by a group of companies in cooperation with scientists
 - **Circular solutions for drink cartons recycling**, by a private Lithuanian and an Italian company, focusing on turning recycled beverage cartons into hygiene paper products

Lithuania

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- **The main barriers are:** Market barriers for secondary resources; Failure of companies to take advantage of CE-related opportunities; Lack of consumers awareness and CE-consistent behavior; Lack of recycling infrastructure; Too much waste is directed to incineration, too little is recycled; In the absence of separate collection for reuse, repairable items are destined to recycling
- **Suggested solutions e.g. include:**
 - Greater attention to the consumer and business sector, through training and knowledge building
 - Focus on consumer demand and fostering sustainable production practices, through strategic (EU) political decisions
 - Cooperation through research and analysis
 - Incentivising businesses to adopt circular business
 - Public procurement, Repair bonus schemes, EPR

Future policy plans

- Lithuania has made progress in implementing several initiatives in **“New Generation Lithuania Plan” 2021–2026**, e.g.:
 - significant upgrades to recycling facilities
 - the share of green public procurement has increased
 - multiple research and innovation projects have been launched, focusing on areas like biodegradable materials, efficient waste-to-energy conversion, and advanced recycling technologies
 - digital tools and platforms to improve waste management efficiency have been introduced and resource tracking has begun
- Lithuania's **National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)** has been updated to include significant measures under the REPowerEU initiative. This is part of the broader European Union strategy to enhance energy security and promote clean energy transitions across Member States. There are various financial resources invested to implement initiatives.

Navarra / Spain

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Spain is 8 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 419.2 million tonnes DMC (6.6 % of EU27 total in 2022) 8.8 tonnes DMC/person (61.7 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 2.6 % Industry: 22.2 % Services: 75.2 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 454,085 people employed in CE sectors (10.6 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 2.3 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010,2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Navarra / Spain

Existing Policy Framework:

- **The Spanish Circular Economy Strategy "Spain 2030"** is being implemented in successive triennial action plans. Following the completion of the **First Circular Economy Action Plan 2021–2023**, work is currently underway on the **Second Circular Economy Action Plan 2024–2026**
 - Mid-term assessment demonstrate a high degree of progress in the implementation of the measures in the first action plan
- Several **regional** (and local) **circular economy strategies, roadmaps, and action plans** have been implemented in Spain – including Navarra Zirkular
- Circular economy is also addressed in the following policies:
 - Sustainable tourism strategy of Spain; Spanish forestry plan; Spanish Social Economy Strategy; Programmes of Measures for the Marine Strategies; Spanish Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy; Strategic Framework for Energy and Climate; Roadmap for the sustainable management of mineral raw materials; Spanish Urban Agenda; Law on the Quality of Architecture; Draft Bill on the Prevention of Food Loss and Food Waste

2/4

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Product-related policies**, e.g. Obsolescence studies; Guide for the development of environmental criteria in the dismantling and repowering of wind power plants
 - **Producer responsibility**, e.g. Register of Product Producer; Development of new EPR schemes
 - **Taxation**, e.g. instruments within Law 7/2022 to reduce waste generation and improve management
 - **Green/Circular/Sustainable public procurement**, e.g. Promoting the European Union Ecolabel; mandatory GPP
 - **Industrial symbiosis**, e.g. by-product and end-of-waste criteria; Market Impact Study; SRM market place
 - Other examples available concerning e.g. **Change in consumption patterns and consumer behaviors, Education and awareness-raising**, and **PPPs**
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - There are examples from 8 sectors, including **Electronics & ICT, Plastics, Packaging, Textiles, Construction and Buildings, Water, Agriculture, and Tourism**

Navarra / Spain

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- **Catalogues of Best Practices in Circular Economy** provide information on the main barriers faced by participating companies in implementing circular economy activities, e.g. including: Barriers to the development of circular business models; Barriers to the development of circular technologies; Administrative barriers
- **New regulations, measures and initiatives** have been introduced to boost CE and address barriers/challenges, e.g:
 - A new domestic regime for the approval of by-products and end-of-waste criteria
 - Aid scheme for CE
 - Pact to promote the adoption of CE strategy/plans by companies
 - Special fiscal regime for product donations
 - Food hierarchy to reduce food waste
 - Ban on the destruction or landfilling of textiles, toys, and electronic devices
 - Good practice guidelines for charitable giving

Future policy plans

- **Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan (RTRP):**
 - Comprehensive plan that allocates 40.29% of Spain's budget to green transition initiatives, in line with the European Green Deal. CE is a key focus, integrated into various components of the plan.
 - Component 12 is a key component for CE, with several investments and actions to support implementation of the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy and Waste Regulations, as well as providing aid to key sectors of the CE (e.g. textiles, plastics, and renewable energy)
 - The RTRP includes significant investments to improve waste management, including digital solutions

Helsinki-Uusimaa / Finland

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Finland is 2.5 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 257.2 million tonnes DMC (4.0 % of EU27 total in 2022) 46.3 tonnes DMC/person (325.4 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 2.8 % Industry: 27.1 % Services: 70.1 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 41,744 people employed in CE sectors (1.0 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.5 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010,2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Helsinki-Uusimaa / Finland

Existing Policy Framework:

- **The Circular Economy Strategic Programme** was adopted in 2021. The interim evaluation indicates that the mandate and implementation are insufficient, the National Audit Office of Finland is currently assessing coordination and management
- **Other initiatives at the national level** e.g. include R&D, implementation of Circular Economy Green Deal, the hub Circular Economy Finland (KiSu), and an innovation fund
- Circular economy is also **addressed in the following policies**: National procurement strategy; National Waste Plan; Plastics Roadmap; Finland’s Architectural Policy Programme; National Food Waste Roadmap
- Regional and local initiatives include **Circular Cities and Regions Initiative** (CCRI) – where Helsinki-Uusimaa is a pilot region
 - Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Valley was created in 2022 for supporting the 2030 carbon neutrality goal, systemic change and circular transition, working on CE in construction, plastics and textiles, food and electronics
 - The Circular Valley Handbook includes exemplary models of CE: pilots, business collaborations, and other activities

2/4

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Research**, e.g. four research institutes (Finnish Environment Institute, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Natural Resources Institute Finland Luke, the Geological Survey of Finland GTK and Statistics Finland) produced a national-level material flow analysis, along with three scenarios on the future of natural resource use in Finland
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - **New business models**, e.g. Finnish Innovation Fund **Sitra** has compiled a list of most interesting companies in the circular economy in Finland, representing the following business models: product-life extension, product as service, sharing platforms, renewability and resource-efficiency and recycling. **Sitra, together with Deloitte**, have also published the Circular economy playbook, which helps companies to unlock circular economy opportunities.

Helsinki-Uusimaa / Finland

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- The concept of **circular economy is familiar to Finnish companies** and the majority see it as an opportunity. **Concrete measures are still quite rare** in companies.
- One **barrier** consists of **skills gap**: many companies need information on concrete measures to strengthen the company's circular economy business.
- According to a survey, 69% of companies have not commissioned emissions **calculations, material reviews, or life cycle assessments**. Additionally, 51% of companies do not organize **training for personnel** on circular economy practices.

Future policy plans

- **Finland's Recovery and Resilience Facility Plan (RRF)**:
 - Strategic promotion of the circular economy and reform of the Waste Act (reform)
 - Re-use and recycling of key materials and industrial side streams (investment)
 - Low-carbon built environment programme (investment)
 - Key programmes for international growth (investment)

Wallonia / Belgium

1/4

Facts and Figures

- **Circularity Rate:** Belgium is 19 % circular.
- **Use of Materials:** 149.1 million tonnes DMC (2.3 % of EU27 total in 2022) 12.8 tonnes DMC/person (89.7 % of EU27 average per person in 2022)
- **Structure of the economy:** Agriculture: 0.9 % Industry: 20.5 % Services: 78.6 %
- **Employment in circular sectors:** 63,868 people employed in CE sectors (1.5 % of EU total in 2021). People employed expressed as a percentage of total employment: 1.3 % (compared to 2.1 % for EU average in 2021)

Figure 2 Material footprint (raw material consumption), 2010,2019 and 2023, tonnes per person

Source: Eurostat (2024) [env_ac_rme] (accessed 21 August 2024)

Wallonia / Belgium

Existing Policy Framework:

- **Circular Wallonia** was established in 2020. It is divided into five main axes:
 - Supply and production of circular goods and services
 - Consumption and demand of circular goods and services
 - Stakeholder engagement
 - Waste and resource management
 - Priority value chains
- **The implementation report of the Circular Wallonia Strategy** was published in September 2024, which provides an overview of the implementation. It shows that more than 700 organisations were supported in their circular transition between 2021–2023.
- Circular economy is also **addressed in the following policies**: the REGAL Plan (Reducing Food Waste in Wallonia); Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) for Circular Materials

2/4

Innovative Approaches and Good Practices:

- Examples of **public policy initiatives** (national, regional or local)
 - **Product-related policies**, e.g. 167 repair cafés is promoted by the Repair Together Association
 - **Producer/supplier responsibility**, e.g. companies and sectoral federations (textile, wood and furniture, commerce and services) have created a management body for EPR, the non-profit organization Valumat
 - **Research & innovation**, e.g. identification of five areas of strategic innovation; new programs to support technological and non-technological circular innovation
 - **Green/Circular/Sustainable Public Procurement**, e.g. Responsible Public Procurement Strategy; Various Networks; Call for Support in Rethinking Policies
 - **Industrial symbiosis**, e.g. call for projects aimed to support Territorial Development Agencies
- Examples of **private policy initiatives** (sectoral)
 - There are good practice examples regarding **Mettalurgy, batteries & Transport; Plastics; Textiles; Construction and Buildings; Food Industry and Food Systems; Water; Circular Materials**

Wallonia / Belgium

3/4

The Way Forward:

Identifying and addressing barriers and challenges

- The identification of the main barriers and challenges that the Walloon enterprises are facing linked to the implementation of circular economy is currently being done by conducting a literature review and questioning the enterprises with a survey that allows them to explain their main challenges.

Future policy plans

- Some of the measures of **Circular Wallonia** have been included in **the Walloon Recovery Plan**. This package gathers **17 measures** from the circular economy strategy and aims to boost economic development
 - Axis 3 of the Walloon Recovery Plan aims to boost Wallonia's economic development through digitisation, reducing the number of brownfield sites, an ambitious industrial policy and strengthening the CE. Two main aspects are concerned here: the realisation of the potential of the CE and support for the prevention, reuse and recycling of waste.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Project No. 101161155. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix 3

Research and Development in the ECIV Regions

Dalarna/NMS in collaboration with WSP

2025-03-03

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the European Union**

Contents

The purpose of this report is to show, and discuss, results from a compilation of research in the nine ECIV regions.

- **Focus:** Identifying prevalent focus and topics of existing and ongoing research in the nine regions

p. 3 – Approach & Method

p. 5 – Regional level

Approach & Method

Research

To identify existing and ongoing research in the nine ECIV regions, three main approaches have been used, shown to the right.

The focus has not been to read and compile insights from the research identified, but rather to identify focuses, themes and topics.

The results should be interpreted as *indications* of existing and ongoing research in the regions.

Universities

- **Identifying universities** located in the nine regions
- Searching **university websites** to locate relevant faculties, projects, literature

Co-Pilot

- **Asking questions** such as *"what faculties at university X work with circular economy?"*, *"which topics or themes are prevalent for research within circular economy in university X?"*
- **Confirming** information output manually

Literature search

- Searching **Google Scholar** and other search engines with key words such as *"circular economy university X"*, *"circular economy region X"*, *"circular economy professor x"*

Regional (& National level)

North Middle Sweden

Existing and Ongoing Research (1/2)

University of Gävle (Högskolan i Gävle)

- Conducts research within Environmental Science, where resource management is a thematic area. Studies on e.g. circular business models, waste management, and recycling infrastructure – with broader scopes and in certain sectors such as construction, manufacturing, energy, and transports.
- Ongoing research projects relating to circular economy include “GENIUS” (focusing on industrial and urban symbiosis in the region), and “Ökad cirkularitet” / Increased circularity (investigating opportunities for increased circularity of goods, textiles and construction materials)
- Previous research projects relating to circular economy include “Crea-RE” (2018–2020, focusing on resource efficiency and circular economy within universities), and “Rutbeck” (2019–2021, focusing on how Swedish regions can prepare for circular transitions)

1/2

Karlstad University (Karlstad universitet)

- Conducts research primarily relating to circular bioeconomy, where ongoing research projects include “Pro2BE” (interdisciplinary research program focusing on the transition to a bioeconomy based on renewable resources and the development of the forest industry), and “WoodVALOR” (EU project focusing on sustainably converting used wood into high-performance paints, coatings, and biochar)
- Other examples of research within circular economy e.g. relate to Consumer Psychology and Innovation (e.g. within the project Rundgång, a recycling mall)
- A new research project has recently started up, “Interregional Circularity in Central Scandinavia”, focusing on promoting sustainable growth and innovation in Värmland and Norwegian Innlandet

North Middle Sweden

2/2

Existing and Ongoing Research (2/2)

Dalarna University (Högskolan i Dalarna)

- The Sustainable Energy Research Center (SERC) integrates various research areas such as energy, sustainable construction, urban planning, computer science, industrial and materials engineering, economics and social sciences. Studies have been conducted on e.g. improving circular principles within buildings, sustainable renovations, and energy-positive neighbourhoods
- Ongoing research projects include “Opportunities and tools to improve circularity in large cross-laminated timber (CLT) buildings”, “More efficient test environments in the construction and real estate sector”, “Synergize building renovation and regenerative urban furniture to co-create PED ecosystems”, and “Linking SDG compliance for balanced energy-positive neighborhoods”

Northern Netherlands

Existing and Ongoing Research

University of Groningen

- Conducts research within the faculties of Economics and Business, and Science and Engineering, e.g. on logistics of biomass and biogas within a circular economy, circular business models, and circular economy practices in the hospitality industry
- Grants are being allocated for further research aimed at advancing more sustainable practices in various areas of circular agriculture

NHL Stenden University of Applied Sciences

- Professorship of Circular Plastics, working on several projects to achieve innovations in the field of circular plastics
- Professorship of Sustainability in Hospitality and Tourism, e.g. the project "Circular Economy in Hospitality"

Hanze University of Applied Sciences

- Conducts research primarily through its Research Centre Biobased Economy, e.g. a professorship relating to transition towards a circular economy
- The Interreg Europe project WEEEWaste focuses on improving policies for waste management of electrical and electronic equipment

Van Hall Larenstein University of Applied Sciences

- Applied research group collaborating on sustainable regional transitions and nature-inclusive circular agriculture
- Research project on circular water in the neighbourhood

Scotland

Existing and Ongoing Research

University of Glasgow

- Leads the “Responsible Electronics and Circular Technologies Centre” (REACT) which focuses on advancing sustainable electronics through innovative research and development
- Hosts the Centre for Sustainable Solutions, which offers courses and conducts research on sustainable business models for a circular economy

University of Edinburgh

- Hosts various research projects and centers dedicated to sustainability and the circular economy, focusing on areas such as design for durability, material efficiencies, plastics recycling, and circular business models

University of Sterling

- Collaboration with Zero Waste Scotland exploring the ways in which conditions need to improve if Scotland’s economy is to become more circular and businesses are to achieve the resultant benefits

Heriot-Watt University ...

- The project “A Circular Scotland in Europe”, together with several other institutions, focusing on overcoming post-Brexit challenges to deliver on internationalisation, circular economy and sustainability
- The iNetZ+ Net Zero and Beyond is a global research institute at Heriot-Watt University, dedicated to achieving net-zero carbon emissions and advancing sustainable practices, e.g. research projects within circular materials, green business and finance, manufacturing and industry

The University of Strathclyde

- The university has two prominent research focuses: Waste, Energy & the Circular Economy (covering topics such as the reuse of organic wastes, recycling of soils and sediments, and the recovery of hazardous wastes), Triple Helix and the role of networks of innovation (examines how partnerships can drive sustainable development, and e.g. focuses on the conservation and sustainable use of resources, linking these efforts to the circular economy)

Gabrovo

Existing and Ongoing Research

The Technical University of Gabrovo

- Hosts programs in engineering, technology and economics, where research regarding circular economy is primarily found within the Faculty of economics
- Research focus mainly the reuse of waste material, where studies have been conducted on closed-loop production systems, the 6R principles (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Recover, Redesign, and Remanufacture), and the structure and dynamics of patent activity in the field of reuse of waste materials
- Associated strategic partner of the Circular Innovation Hub (CI-HUB), a collaborative initiative aimed at enhancing the innovation potential in less developed regions by promoting circular economy practice

Normandy

Existing and Ongoing Research

EM Normandie

- Is deeply involved in advancing the circular economy through its European Chair of Excellence on Circular Economy and Territories
- The chair focuses on several key areas, including e.g. The drivers and barriers to the circular transition; Identifying and highlighting inspiring projects in responsible consumption, reuse, recycling, and waste valorization across Europe; Circular business models
- The chair also promotes circular economy through awareness-raising, and advocacy, offering training and workshops to support the circular transition

Université de Rouen Normandie

- Research in sustainability and environmental sciences, which can encompass aspects of the circular economy – mainly relating to Industrial and Territorial Ecology, and Energy

Lithuania

Existing and Ongoing Research

Kaunas University of Technology

- Current project includes “CEPOC” (Managing Paradoxical Tensions and Developing Organizational Capabilities in a Circular Economy), which focuses on understanding and managing tensions that arise in organizations transitioning to a circular economy
- Previous research has e.g. focused on circular business models (e.g. in manufacturing industry), sustainability reporting and management, and circular design and interdisciplinary networking

ISM University of Management and Economics

- Member of the “Circular Economy Alliance”, which implements circular economy projects globally
- Engaged in the EU project “POP-MACHINA”, which aims to enhance circular economy through collaborative production – ISM researchers are studying consumer behavior to encourage the use of circular economy items

Vilnius University

- Engaged in the “CIRCLE” project, which aims to promote sustainable and circular use of bioresources across agriculture, forestry, and aquaculture in the Baltic-Nordic region – VU researchers are studying consumer behaviour and ethical perspectives on the circular economy

Vytautas Magnus University

- Specializes in environmental sustainability and the application of circular economy practices in agriculture, bioeconomy and rural development

Navarra

Existing and Ongoing Research

University of Navarra

- Institute of Biodiversity and Environment focuses on integrating sustainability and circular economy principles into various aspects of society and the economy
- Some key areas of research include Sustainable and Biodegradable Materials; Waste Valorization; Circular Biotechnology; Water Treatment; and Sustainable Urban Planning

Public University of Navarra

- Chair of Transfer and Innovation in Circular Economy

Generation of knowledge in the area of the circular economy, allowing the integration of the academic and business worlds, promoting conditions that favor the conduct of advanced research and the transfer of knowledge related to this area to the productive sector

Support is provided for the completion of doctoral theses and final projects (undergraduate and master's degrees), and the granting of scholarships and awards for the development of research and work related to the circular economy will be promoted.

- Master in Circular Economy

Acquire multidisciplinary training, from scientific and technical to economic and legal aspects, essential for implementing circular economy principles in public and private companies and institutions.

Helsinki-Uusimaa

Existing and Ongoing Research

University of Helsinki

- Institute of Sustainable Science (HELSUS) conducts research on circular economy – e.g. the project “recycling Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment” (WEEE)
- Research group in chemistry of circular economy investigates conversion technologies for better implementation of circular economy
- Other areas of research include bioeconomy, food and agriculture, and engaging citizens in the circular economy

Aalto University

- The Department of Management studies have two ongoing projects: “FINIX” and “Circular Design Network”, focusing on sustainable textiles
- Research group on “Circular Biobased Materials”
- “The Circular Raw Materials Hub” was a collaboration with the Geological Survey of Finland, and VTT

Laurea University of Applied Sciences

- Service Business and Circular Economy RDI Platform – focusing implementation of business ecosystems
- Projects that aim to improve the reuse of textiles and reduce textile waste in the textile market, e.g. “Baltic2Hand”
- Projects that aim to reduce food waste and utilise it more efficiently, e.g. “Food waste ecosystem”

Wallonia

Existing and Ongoing Research

Université catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain)

- Research particularly in Engineering and Environmental Science, e.g. studies on developing circular business models, promoting sustainable practices, and addressing environmental justice issues, and exploring the role of stakeholders in this process.
- One of their ongoing research projects is “Analysing and Identifying the Circular Economy’s contribution to a just Transition” (AICE-T).

Université de Liège (Uliège)

- Involved in projects focused on waste management, resource efficiency, and sustainable production
- One of their ongoing research projects is “UniGR-CIRKLA”, which aims to efficiently manage critical raw materials and promote recycling of technological resources and waste

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Project No. 101161155. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.